

Index des graphies non-standard et gloses mentionnées dans P. Delnero, SANER 26 (2020) (choix)¹

1) Plan des pages 527-649²

II List of Phonetic Writings by the Groups of Sources in which they Occur: 527-578

- Identifiable Sub-groups: 527-556
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 527-541
 - Sandhi writings: 541-543
 - Omission of Determinatives: 543
 - Other distinctive writings: 543
- Kish: 544-552
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 544-550
 - Sandhi Writings: 550 sq.
 - Omission of Determinatives: 551 sq.
 - Other Unusual Writings: 552
- Girsu/Telloh (NFT): 552-555
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 552-554
 - Sandhi Writings: 554
 - Omission of Determinatives: 555
- Nippur: 555 sq.
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 555
 - Sandhi Writings: 555 sq.
- Tell Harmal: 556
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 556
 - Sandhi Writings: 556
 - Omission of Determinatives: 556
- Other Sources: 557-569
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 557-566
 - Sandhi Writings: 567-569
 - Omission of Determinatives: 569
- Phonetic Writings – Incantations (Selective): 569-575
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 570-574
 - Omission of Determinatives: 575
 - Sandhi Writings: 575
- Phonetic Writings in Royal Inscriptions: 576-
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 576 sq.
 - Sandhi Writings: 577
- Phonetic Writings in sources for Shulgi Hymn A: 577 sq.
 - Phonetic Writings (words and word units): 577 sq.
 - Sandhi Writings: 578

III List of Phonetic Writings by Type: 578-649

- Homophonous Signs: 578-587
- Polysyllabic Words: 587-608
 - i. Polysyllabic Words: 587-603
 - ii. Polysyllabic Forms (CV, VC, and words with grammatical element): 603-608
- Consonant Reduplication Avoided: 608-610
- Sandhi Writings: 611-618
 - Laments: 611-617
 - Kish: 612-614
 - Girsu: 614
 - Nippur: 614
 - Harmal: 614
 - Remaining Sources: 614-617
 - Incantations: 617 sq.
 - Royal Inscriptions: 618
 - Decad: 618

¹ Les morphèmes grammaticaux n'ont pas été pris en considération. Attinger, GSF = P. Attinger, Glossaire sumérien-français, principalement des textes littéraires paléobabyloniens (2021).

² La structure des pp. 527-649 étant extrêmement complexe, j'essaye d'en donner le plan ci-dessous. Je ne suis toutefois pas certain d'avoir toujours bien compris les intentions de l'auteur. L'usage quelque peu déroutant des majuscules et des minuscules suit l'original.

- Omission of Determinative: 618-620
 - Laments: 618-620
 - Kish: 619 sq.
 - Girsu: 620
 - < Remaining Sources:> 620
 - Incantations: 620
- Less Common Writings: 620-649
 - I. Extra Phonemes: 620-622
 - /q/: 620 sq.
 - /y/: 621 sq.
 - II. Defective Writings: 622-625
 - i. Omission of Vowel: 622
 - a. initial position: 622
 - b. medial position: 622
 - c. final position: 622
 - ii. Omission of Consonant: 622 sq.
 - a. medial position: 622-624
 - b. final position: 624
 - iii. Vocalic and Consonantal Ellisions: 625
 - iv. Loss of Gemination: 625
 - III. Morpho-phonological Elaboration: 625-630
 - i. Final vowel added (plene): 625
 - ii. Final consonant added (plene): 625 sq.
 - iii. Disambiguation of Vowels: 626
 - iv. Voicing of Consonants: 626-629
 - /g/ > /k/ or /q/: 626 sq.
 - /b/ > /p/: 628
 - /t/ > /d/: 628
 - /n/ > /m/ or /ḡ/: 628 sq.
 - v. Phonetic rendering of reduplicated forms: 629 sq.
 - IV. Phonetic Variation: 630-646
 - i. Vowel harmony: 630-632
 - ii. Phonetic Shifts: 632-646
 - a. Vowel: 632-636
 - ai. e > i, i > e: 632-636
 - aii. a > i, i > a: 636
 - aiii. u > i: 636
 - aiv. others: 636
 - b. Consonant
 - bi. g > k, k > g, g/k > q: 636-639
 - bii. b > p, p > b: 639-641
 - biii. d > t, t > d: 641 sq.
 - biv. m > n, n > m: 642
 - bv. ḡ > k, m, n and g: 643 sq.
 - bvi. š > s: 644 sq.
 - bvii. m > b/p: 645
 - bviii. s > z: 645.
 - bix. others: 646
 - V. More than one change – Entire Words and Phrases: 646 sq.
 - <VI>(?) Other: 647-649
 - Other Unusual Writings: 648 sq.
 - Laments: 648 sq.
 - Kish: 649
 - Haddad: 649

2) Liste des graphies non-standard³

³ A quelques exceptions près, les lectures sont celles de Delnero et n'ont pas été vérifiées sur les copies et/ou les photos de CDLI. Remarquer par ailleurs que nombre des identifications proposées entre graphies non-standard et graphies standard semblent très hypothétiques, quoiqu'il ne soit naturellement pas exclu qu'elles reposent sur des passages parallèles dont j'ignore l'existence.

Le lecteur trouvera ci-dessous une liste des graphies non-standard mentionnées dans SANER 26 avec les renvois aux pages où elles sont discutées (point 2; type a = e₃-a 568, 569, 578, 616, 617, 618), suivie d'une liste des lexèmes dont une ou plusieurs graphies non-standard sont attestées (point 3; type a-eštub → e-a-tu-ub, e₂-a-tu-ub, e₂-a-aš-tu-ub). Le travail d'indexation a été compliqué par un double fait:

— Delnero ne distingue pas clairement les formes ES des formes EG (e.g. i-gi = i-bi₂, mu-ni₅-in-ma-ar = ^{giš}nim-mar, sila₄-amar = sila₃-ġar, šu-mu = ^{u2}NUNUN₂, etc.; v. les notes ad loc.).

— Il cite le plus souvent les formes avec suffixes, sans préciser l'analyse, ce qui complique singulièrement l'interprétation des graphies. Ainsi hu-lu/ħul-lu peut en principe recouvrir /ħulu/ ou /ħul(u) + e/, i-si-ši /isiš/ ou /isiš + e/, ki-is₃-ki-ra /kiskil/ (+ /'a/) ou /kiskil + ra/, etc.

A quelques exceptions près, le système de translittération utilisé reflète les choix de Delnero, pas les miens propres (v. en général Attinger, GSF).

Noter les conventions suivantes: * = dans les textes lexicaux, (*) = dans les textes lexicaux et en contexte, Ø = seulement en contexte.

a: → e₄.

a = a₂: 271, 528, 544, 557, 576, 578 sq.; → en-a-nu-un.

a = aġ₂⁴: 279:5, 567.

a = AK: 528, 579.

a = am: 541, 611.

a = an: 529, 541, 567, 614.

a = e₃-a: 568, 569, 578, 616, 617, 618.

a-b = ab: → a-a-ba.

a-d = ad: 570, 603.

"a-m = am"⁵: 552, 554, 603, 608, 614.

a-n = an: 102:4, 168, 231, 251, 267 (dans u₃-šu-gal-a-na), 269 (id.), 317:2, 344:99, 529, 540 (dans u₃-šu-gal-a-na), 541, 543 (dans u₃-šu-gal-a-na), 544, 550, 551 (dans [sa₁₂]-du₅-a-na), 552, 557 (dans u₃-šu-gal-a-na), 567, 588 (dans u₃-šu-gal-a-na), 603, 604, 608, 611, 612, 613 (dans [sa₁₂]-du₅-a-na), 615, 619 (dans u₃-šu-gal-a-na), 623, 624 (id.), 625, 646 (id.); → e₂-a-na, ama-šu-gal-a-na.

a-q = AK: 341:91.

a-r = ar₂: 577, 618.

a-š = aš (s.v. dili): 545, 647.

a-t = ad₆: 231, 233, 328:38, 544, 550, 613, 641.

a/e₄-y = e₂: V. ya.

a-a-an-na = e₂-an-na: 267, 552, 631.

a-a-ba = a-ab-ba⁶: 251, 554, 614.

a-ar = ir₂: 240:26'.

a-aš₂-pa-la = aš₂-bala: 577, 618.

*a-ba-ar = ambar: 256, 528, 588, 645.

*a-bar = ambar: 256, 528, 588, 645.

a-da = ad-da: 282.

a-du-bu = adab(u)^{ki}: 266, 544, 550, 612, 630.

a-ga-ar = a-gar₃: 570, 587, 629.

a-ga-ar-a-ga-r = a-gar₃-agar₃: 570, 587, 629.

a-ġa₂-ri-in = aġarin₄: 570, 587.

*a-ka = KA₂: 562, 644, 648.

a-la = a-la₂: 280, 570, 575, 578, 617.

a-la-n = alan: 281, 570, 587.

a-li = alim (dans a-li(-) ma-ħa = alim maħ-a): 567, 614.

a-li-m = alim: 544, 557, 588.

*a-li-im = alim: 544, 557, 588.

(*)a-ma = ama: 250, 271, 528, 544, 555, 557, 588, 647.

a-ma-s = amaš: 265, 267, 270, 528, 544, 550, 552, 588, 612, 636, 644.

(*)a-ma-aš₂ = amaš: 258, 265, 267, 528, 557, 588, 644.

a-ma-lu = amalu: 286, 570, 588.

⁴ Ici et passim, Delnero translittère la forme ES de niġ₂ eġ₃; les graphies non-standard rassemblées par lui (a, am-, an et (r)a-ġ) plaident toutefois clairement pour aġ₂.

⁵ a-me ba-ra-na dans NFT 207 iv 4 (sic, pas "r. iv' 4") n'est pas une graphie non-standard de am-e bara₂ an-na (ainsi Delnero 554 et 614), mais de a-ġe₆ ¹⁷buranuna (cf. A. Poebel, ZA 37 [1927] 162 sq. et comm. pp. 269 sq. et en dernier lieu K. Volk, FAOS 18 [1989] 225 sq.).

⁶ Dans G₆ o. iii 7, lire a-a-ba, pas a-a-bi (ainsi Delnero).

a-ma-u₂-šu-ga-la-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 555, 588, 614, 646.
 a-nin = a-gin⁷: 231, 269, 544, 646.
 a-nu-ĝa₂ = a₂-nu-ĝal₂: 335:71, 554, 614.
 a-nu-na = ^da-nun-na: 528, 608, 625.
 a-pa-ap = a-pap: 570, 587.
 a-pa-ar = ambar: 256, 275, 529, 557, 588, 628, 645.
 a-ra-b = adab^{ki7}: 557, 587.
 a-ra-a = a-ri-a: 266, 557, 631.
 a-ra-ta = aratta^{ki}: 231, 234, 252, 347:105, 544, 551, 557, 588, 619.
 a-ra-^rta₃^{7?} = aratta^{ki}: 347:105, 557, 588.
 a/e₄-ri-du^{ki} = eridu^{ki}: 265, 266, 531, 592, 636.
 a-sa-g = a₂-sig₃: 567, 615.
 a-sa-l = ^{ĝis}asal₂⁸: 557, 569, 589, 620.
 a-sa-r = ^dasar: 283, 570, 589.
 a-sa-al = ^{ĝis}asal₂⁹: 544, 551, 589, 619.
 a-sa-al-lu-ĥi = ^dasal-lu₂-ĥi: 281, 283, 570, 589.
 a-ša = a-ša₃: 249, 271, 280, 528, 578, 622.
 a-ša-g = a-ša₃-g: 570, 578.
 a-ši = anše: → maš-a-ši.
 a-ši-r = a-še-er: 240:26', 264, 528, 632.
 a-ši-ir = a-še-er: 240:15', 264, 374 bas, 528, 557, 632.
 a-tu-ub = eštub: → e-a-tu-ub, e₂-a-tu-ub.
 a-u₂-r = a₂-ur₂: 528, 603.
 a-u₃-r = a₂-ur₂: 528, 603.
 a-u₃-ur = a₂-ur₂: 557, 579.
 a-u₄-r = a₂-ur₂: 544, 603.
 a-ur = a₂-ur₂: 544, 579.
 a-ur₂ = a₂-ur₂: 528, 557, 579.
 (*)a-ya = a-a: 254, 284, 528, 544, 557, 567, 570, 615, 621.
 a-ya-gu = a-a-ugu: 567, 615.
 a₂ = a: 231.
 a₂-nu-ĝal₂ = a₂-nun-ĝal₂: 577, 622.
 ab = ab₂: 528, 579.
 *ab-ba-ar = ambar: 256, 275, 528, 588, 645.
 *ab-bar = ambar: 256, 528, 588, 645.
 ab-ka-l = abgal: 256, 528, 587, 626, 636.
 ab-la-al = ab-lal₃: 238:5', 528, 587.
 ab-si(-n) = ab-sin₂¹⁰: 570, 587.
 ab-si-im = ab-sin₂: 257, 557, 628, 642, 647.
 *ab-si-in: 257, 557, 642, 647.
 ab-za = abzu (dans ab-za-a = ab-zu-a); 570, 587, 631.
 (*)ab-zu = abzu: 528, 557, 570, 587.
 *ad = ad₆: 544, 641.
 ad-te-r = addir: 256, 552, 587, 628, 641.
 aĝ₂ = an: 257, 557, 628, 643.
 aĝ₂-ba-ra-ga = aĝ₂-bara₃-ga: 269, 559, 592, 643.
 aĝ₂-ma-l = aĝ₂-ma-al: 567, 615.
 (a)ĥ-la = ĥul-a: 282, 575, 617.
 al = an (dans al-lu₂-gal): 251, 541, 611.
 al-ĝa₂-ar-sur-ra = ^{ĝis}al-ĝar-sur-ra: 544, 551, 587, 619.
 al-la = lil₂-la₂: 548, 596.
 al-lu = a-la-lu: 557, 647.
 am = ama: 552, 622 647.
 am-ba-ra-ga = aĝ₂-bara₃-ga: 269, 559, 592, 643.
 am-išib-gal-an-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 268, 552, 554, 588, 614, 646; → am-išib-gal-an-na.
 am₃ = am: 557, 579.

⁷ Il n'y a pas de raison de corriger -ra- en -da!- (ainsi Delnero). Pour a-ra-b = adab, v. en dernier lieu G. Marchesi, MC 14 (2006) 169 n. 87.

⁸ Delnero ^{ĝis}asal est une coquille.

⁹ V. la note précédente.

¹⁰ Cf. Attinger, GSF 131.

ama-s = amaš: 231, 267, 270, 318:7, 544, 588, 644.
 ama-gu₂ = ama-ugu: 444, 544, 550, 613, 647.
 ama-lu = amalu: 286, 570, 588.
 ama-lu₂ = amalu: 286, 552, 588.
 ama-maš = amaš¹¹: 557, 644, 647.
 ama-šu-ga-la-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 293, 541, 543, 588, 611, 618, 646.
 ama-šu-gal-a-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 268, 528, 557, 567, 588, 615, 646.
 ama-šu-gal-la-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 269, 557, 567, 588, 615, 646.
 ama-šu-mu-gal-la-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 268, 557, 567, 588, 615, 646.
 ama-u₃-šu-gal-la-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 268, 269, 528, 557, 567, 588, 615, 646.
 ama-u₃-šu-um-gal-an-na = ama-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 529, 588, 646.
 amar = ġar: → sila₄-amar.
 a(n) = a₂: 541, 611.
 an = aġ₂: 559, 636, 643.
 an-de-el = an-dul₃¹²: 542, 612.
 an-di-n = an-edin: 541, 611.
 an-di-il₃¹³ = an-dul₃: 529, 647.
 an-pa₃ = an-pa: 537, 541, 584, 611.
 an-ši = anše: 557, 588, 632.
 ap-pa-r = ambar: 256, 275, 528, 588, 628, 645.
 ap-pa-ar = ambar: 231, 256, 275, 341:94, 544, 570, 588, 628, 645.
 ar-ġu-š = arġuš: 529, 589.
 *ar-ġu-uš = arġuš: 529, 589.
 as₃-s = aš (partiellement s. v. dili): 557, 647.
 (a)Š(-)si-la = sila: 543, 612.
 aš-ta-am = eš₂-dam: → (d)a-aš-ta-am = e₂-eš₂-dam: 283, 575, 617.
 aš-ti = aš-te: 529, 557, 632.
 aš-tu-ub = eštub: → e₂-a-aš-tu-ub.
 (a)š₂-re = sar-re: 577, 618.
 at-t = ad₆: 231, 233, 328:39, 544, 550, 613, 641.
 ba-d = bad₃: 544, 567, 604, 608.
 ba-d = pad₃: 537, 548, 606, 610, 640.
 ba-r = bar (subst. et vb.): 529, 544, 558, 569, 575, 604, 608, 613, 617; → eš-ba-r, ru-ba-r, ur₂-ba-ra.
 *ba-ab-ba-ar = babbar: 256, 262, 267, 275, 529, 589, 625, 628, 640.
 (*)ba-ad = bad: 529, 589.
 ba-ad = bad₃: 555, 589.
 ba-an-da = ban₃-da: 262, 558, 589, 641.
 ba-an-su-r = ġis¹⁴bansur: 283, 571, 589, 640.
 ba-an-su-ur = ġis¹⁴bansur: 262, 283, 529, 558, 589, 640.
 *ba-an-šur = ġis¹⁴bansur: 256, 262, 558, 589, 640.
 ba-ap-pa-ar = babbar: 285, 570, 589, 628, 640.
 (*)ba-ar = bar: 529, 544, 558, 589, 604.
 ba-ba-r = babbar: 262, 267, 275, 285, 529, 556, 589, 625, 640.
 ba-ba-ar = bar-bar: 254, 529, 547, 604, 629, 640.
 (*)ba-ba-ar = babbar: 256, 262, 267, 275, 285, 529, 589, 625, 628, 640.
 *ba-da = bad: 529, 589.
 ba-di-bi-ra = bad₃-tibira^{ki}: 529, 543, 589, 618, 641.
 ba-la = bala: 552, 558, 589; → ki-ba-la.
 ba-la-ġ = balaġ: 250, 558, 567, 589, 615.
 ba-la-aġ₂ = balaġ: 250, 529, 544, 558, 589.
 ba-pa-r = babbar: 256, 262, 267, 270, 275, 285, 544, 589, 625, 628, 640.
 "ba-ra = bara₂"¹⁴: 262, 552, 554, 589, 614, 640.
 ba-ra(-g) = bara₃(-g): 558, 589; → aġ₂-ba-ra-ga, am-ba-ra-ga.
 bad = bad₃: 281, 570, 579.
 bad-bi-ra = bad₃-tibira^{ki}: 259, 529, 543, 589, 619, 646.
 ban₃-ta = ban₃-da: 262, 544, 641.

¹¹ Le contexte est clair (cf. E. Bergmann, ZA 56 [1964] 1 et commentaire p. 12), mais l'interprétation de la graphie pas évidente.

¹² Cf. ad "sa₂ = saġ".

¹³ Delnero an-DI.AN; sur an-dil₃(⁻) plutôt que an-dul₃/dul₇, v. en dernier lieu Attinger, GSF 171 avec n. 296.

¹⁴ Cf. la note à propos de a-m; a-ma ba-ra-na n'est pas une graphie non-standard de am-e bara₂ an-na (ainsi Delnero 554 et 614), mais de a-ġe₆ ¹⁷buranuna.

bar = babbar/bar₆; → di-li-bar = ^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂.
 bar^{ar} = bar: 543, 648.
 bar-du-ul = bar-dul₅: 531, 604.
 (b)e₂-d = e₃-d: 568, 615.
 (b)e₂-kur = e₂-kur: 265, 565, 569¹⁵, 607, 616, 634.
 (b)i-r = i-r: 233, 320:12 sq., 550, 613.
 bi-š = peš₁₀: 233, 330:50, 549, 573, 599, 607, 640.
 bi-ir = bir₅: 571, 590.
 bi-ir-bi-r = bir₇-bir₇: 530, 629.
 bi-iš = peš₂: 573, 599, 640.
 bi-iš = peš₁₀: 233, 330:50, 367, 376, 549, 599, 640.
 bi-la = bil₂-la₂¹⁶: 564, 583, 640.
 bi-la-bi = bil₍₂₎-la₂-bi¹⁷: 346-347:104-105, 374 CBS 106 f. 11'/14', 560, 648.
 bi-ri = biri¹⁸: 530, 604.
 (b)i₂ = e: 559.
 bu: → pu.
 bu-lu-k = bulug: 256, 262, 558, 567, 590, 615, 626, 636.
 (*)bu-lu-ug = bulug: 256, 262, 558, 590, 636.
 bu-ra-na = ¹⁷buranun: 281, 283, 571, 590.
 (*)bu-ru = buru^{musēn}: 231, 234, 252, 281, 341:93, 372, 544, 551, 558, 569, 571, 590, 619, 620.
 bu-ur-bu-r = bur₂-bur₂: 254, 558, 629.
 da = dam: 530, 541, 608, 611, 623.
 da-b = dab₅: 262, 530, 604, 608, 629, 640.
 da-l = dal: 238:6', 530, 604, 608.
 da-m = dam: 359:2 sq. C (ou da-ma), 468:336 (id.), 567, 615¹⁹.
 da-p = dab₅: 256, 262, 530, 604, 608, 628, 640.
 da-p = dib (dans id-da-pa = (?) i₇-da dib-ba): 234, 551, 613.
 da-a-a = ta-e-am₃: 569, 616.
 *da-ab = dab₅: 256, 262, 530, 604, 640.
 (*)da-al = dal: 530, 571, 590, 604.
 da-al-da-dal = dal-dal-dal: 571, 629.
 (d)a-am = ama: 569, 616.
 (*)da-am = dam: 250, 545, 556, 558, 590.
 da-ar-da-r = dar-dar: 254, 530, 629.
 (d)a-aš-ta-am = e₂-eš₂-dam: 283, 575, 617.
 da-da-g = dadag: 281, 530, 558, 571, 590.
 *da-da-ag = dadag: 530, 590.
 da-ġa₂-l = daġal: 252, 268, 530, 558, 571, 590, 643.
 (*)da-ġal₂ = daġal: 268, 530, 558, 571, 590, 643.
 da-ka-l = daġal: 268, 530, 590, 643.
 da-ma = dam: 250, 545, 558, 567, 590, 615; → da-m.
 da-ma-l = daġal²⁰: 268, 545, 590.
 da-ma-al = daġal²¹: 268, 530, 590, 643.
 dalla = dal-la: 578, 618.
 dam-ga-ar = dam-gar₃: 558, 590.
 dam-ga-ra = dam-gar₃: 545, 590.
 dam-ma = dam: "255"²², 344:100 K₁²³, "530", 550 (Delnero diff.), "625, 647".
 de²⁴ = de₂: 281, 530, 558, 571, 579, 632.
 de = de₆: 281, 571, 579.
 de-de-el = di₄-di₄-la₂: 254, 558, 589, 629, 632.

¹⁵ Aux pp. 569 et 616, lire še-eb (pas še-en).

¹⁶ Delnero y voit une graphie non-standard de pel₍₂₎-la.

¹⁷ Delnero y voit à tort une graphie de gibil₍₄₎ (346 n. 17, 560 et 618); sur ce topos, v. en dernier lieu U. Gabbay, HES 2 (2015) 85 avec n. 75.

¹⁸ Delnero bi-re = bir. Pour la lecture biri plutôt que bir, cf. Attinger, GSF 210 sq. avec n. 416.

¹⁹ Pour da-m ou da-ma, v. aussi la note à propos de "dam-ma" dans AO 7697 i 1-3.

²⁰ Probabl. plutôt ES de daġal.

²¹ Probabl. plutôt ES de daġal.

²² Dans AO 7697 i 1-3 (= TCL 16, 78:1-3 = Cohen, Eršemma 71 sqq n° 97 C 1-3), lire da-ma-na, pas dam-ma-na (corriger en conséquence aussi les pp. 530, 625 et 647).

²³ Dans X₂, dam-ma-na peut recouvrir aussi bien dam + /ana/ que dama + /ana/.

²⁴ Delnero translittère selon les cas de ou di.

de-de-le = di₄-di₄-la₂: 254, 558, 590, 629, 632.
 de-de₃-el-le = di₄-di₄-la₂: 319:9, 558.
 *de-e = di: 545, 632.
 *de-e-li = dili: 558, 590.
 de-el-en-babbar²⁵ = ^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂: 268, 530, 543, 590, 619, 646.
 de-me = ^{u2}teme₂: 549, 550, 601, 613.
 de₃-de₃ = de₂-de₂: 558, 579.
 de₃-de₃ = di-di: 545, 632.
 de₃-de₃-la = di₄-di₄-la₂: 232, 254, 319:9, 545, 629, 632.
 de₃-el-le = di₄-di₄-la₂: 232, 254, 319:10, 545, 629, 632.
 di-b = dib: 282, 530, 555, 558, 571, 604, 608, 629, 640.
 di-l = til₃: 256, 262, 269, 539, 607, 628, 642.
 di-m = dim: 283, 575, 617.
 di-m = dim₂: 530, 604; → ni-im-ḥu-lu-di-ma, niḡ₂-ḥu-lu-di-ma.
 di-m = dim₃: 545, 604.
 di-n = edin: 554, 614; → an-di-n.
 di-p = dib: 232, 282, 329:46-48, 366, 545, 604, 608, 628, 640.
 di-di-b = dib-dib: 284, 555, 571, 604, 629.
 di-di(-m) = dim₂-dim₂: 530, 541, 611, 629.
 di-gi-r = diḡir: 558, 591, 643.
 *di-ḡi₆-ir = diḡir²⁶: 531, 591, 643.
 *di-i = di: 545, 632.
 *di-ib = dib: 530, 545, 604, 640.
 di-im = dim₂: 530, 604; → ni-im-di-im-ma.
 di-im-gu-ul = ^{ḡi₈}dimgul: 558, 590.
 di-ku = di-ku₅: 552, 579.
 (*)di-li = dili: 241, 530, 558, 590.
 di-li-babbar₂ = ^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂: 268, 530, 543, 590, 619, 646.
 di-li-bar = ^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂: 268, 558, 646.
 di-lu-ba = tin-ug₅-ba: → ga-ša-an-di-lu-ba.
 di-me-er = dim₃-me-er: 251, 530, 558, 590, 608, 625.
 di-mi-ir = dim₃-me-er: 267, 530, 552, 590, 631.
 di-ne-r = diḡir: 269, 530, 541, 590, 611, 643.
 (*)di-ri = diri: 250, 530, 545, 558, 591.
 DIḠIR^{ḡe₉/ne-r₂₇} = diḡir: 269, 530, 541, 590, 611, 643.
 DIḠIR^{ḡe₉/ne-er₂₈} = diḡir: 269, 530, 541, 590, 611, 643.
 dim₃-me-r = dim₃-me-er: 530, 541, 590, 611.
 dim₃-mi-ir = dim₃-me-er: 99:18', 267, 558, 631.
 du = du₃: 325:26 (cf. id. n. 7), 545, 558, 579.
 du = du₆: 281, 531, 571, 580.
 du = du₇: 232, 249, 275, 531, 558, 571, 580.
 du = du₈: 233, 345:101²⁹, 531, 545, 550, 578, 580, 613; → igi du.
 du = du₁₀: 545, 558, 580; → e-ri-du.
 du = du₁₁: 232, 270, 279:1, 281, 531, 545, 555, 558, 567, 568, 571, 580, 614, 615.
 du = du₁₂: 531, 580.
 du = du₁₄: 324:23.
 du = dug (dans du-gi-in/ki-in/ke-en = dug-gin₇): 283, 575, 617.
 du = tug₂/tu₉³⁰: 256, 262, 565, 586, 628, 642.
 du-d = tu-d: 540, 566, 602, 628, 642.
 du-g = du₁₀-g: → ne-du-g, ni₅-in-du-g.
 du-g = du₁₁-g: 261, 281, 319:10, 531, 580, 636.
 du-k = du₁₁-g: 228, 256, 261, 281, 531, 558, 580, 626, 636, 637.
 du(-k) = dug (dans du-ki-in/ke-en = dug-gin₇/gen₇): 283, 575, 617.
 du-l = dul: 531, 559, 604, 608.

²⁵ Delnero lit di-il₅-.

²⁶ Delnero: di-mi-ir = dingir.

²⁷ Delnero AN-ne-r.

²⁸ Delnero AN-ne-er.

²⁹ K₁ a i-bi a-mi-du, suivi de Ø i-ga-du-u₄ (pour l'abrégement des composés avec {inga}, cf. ELS 298 § 196 Rem.). -du-u₄ recouvre plus probabl. -du₈-e (ainsi Delnero 233, 550 et 613) que -du₈.

³⁰ V. la note à propos de (*)tu = tug₂/tu₉.

du-q = du₁₁-g: 254, 256, 270, 281, 284, 320 sq.:14 sq., 322:17 sq., 349:109, 545, 551, 571, 580, 614, 620, 626, 637.
 du-r = dur₂: → du-ru.
 du-bu-r = dubur: 545, 591.
 du-bu-ra-na = dubur-an-na: 251, 530, 541, 550, 591, 611, 613.
 du-du = du₃-du₃: 558, 567, 579, 615.
 du-du = du₁₂-du₁₂: 559, 567, 580, 615.
 (*)du-gu-ud = dugud: 559, 591.
 *du-li = dili: 558, 590.
 "du-mu = du₅-mu"³¹: 531, 591.
 (*)du-mu = dumu: 262, 545, 559, 576, 591, 641.
 du-ra = dur₁₁-ra³²: 232, 275, 326:33, 363, 545, 591.
 du-ra-an-ki = dur-an-ki: 567, 615.
 du-ra-du-ra = dur₂-ra-dur₂-ra; 531, 629.
 du-ra-ki = dur-an-ki: 559, 623, 646.
 du-ru/du-r = dur₂: 552, 604, 609, 629.
 (*)du-ru = duru₅: 275, 545, 559, 591.
 du-ru = durun: 336:76.
 du-ru-n = durun/dur₂-ru-un: 552, 559, 591, 604, 609, 629.
 du-ru-du-ru-n = durun-durun: 552, 604, 609, 629.
 du-si = dusi₂: 559, 591.
 du-tu = du₈-du₈: 571.
 *du-u₂ = du₃: 545, 580.
 *du-u₂ = du₇: 275.
 *du-ub = dub: 559, 604, 641.
 du-ub³-sa-ar = dub-sar: 283, 575, 617.
 *du-ud-du = du₁₂-du₁₂: 539, 601.
 *du-ul = dul: 531, 604.
 du-ul = dul₅: → bar-du-ul.
 *du-ur = dur₂: 552, 604, 629.
 du-^rx^r-ar-ra-na = dubur-an-na: 556, 614.
 du₃ = du₇: 232, 233, 249, 251, 269, 275, 327:36, 545, 550, 580, 613.
 du₇ = du₁₁: 578, 580.
 du₈ = du₁₀: → eri-du₈.
 du₈ = du₁₁: 558, 580.
 du₁₀ = du₇: → he₂-du₁₀.
 du₁₀-gu = dungu: 284, 571, 623.
 du₁₀-sa-r = dub-sar: 283, 284, 571, 575, 617, 623.
 dub = dub₂: 324:25, 545, 580, 640, 641.
 dub-sa-r = dub-sar: 545, 591.
 dug = du₁₁-g: 575, 617.
 dumu^{mu} = dumu: 541, 543, 611, 648.
 duru₅ⁿⁱ = dur₁₁-ra³³: 326-327:33.
 (*)e = e₂: 232, 238:1', 249, 271, 274 sq., 334:68, 336:74, 352-353:118, 531, 546, 552, 555, 559, 576, 580 sq.
 (*)e = e₃: 251, 531, 542, 552, 559, 567, 568, 571, 576, 581, 611, 615; → pa₃-e, su-pa₃-e.
 (*)e = e₄³⁴/a: 232, 322 sq.:17 sq., 528, 546, 559, 570, 578, 581.
 e = i³⁵: 534, 561, 568, 616, 633, 648.
 *e = i₇: 547, 582, 625.
 e-n = en: 575, 617.
 "e-y = e₂": V. e₂-y.
 e-a-tu-ub = a-eštub: 257, 528, 622.
 e-di-n = edin: 531, 559, 591.
 e-ga-r = engar: 284, 571, 623,

³¹ Dans BM 78198 o. 14', lire e-ge-en ki du-ġu₁₀ nu-zu "comme l'eau, j'ignore le lieu où je vais" (cf. M. Jaques, OBO 273 [2015] 45 et 343 et Attinger, GSF 310 n. 734).

³² D'après Delnero (surtout p. 363), du-ra serait une graphie non-standard de duru₅. LSU 379 prouve sans équivoque possible que dans ce topos, du-ra et duru₅ⁿⁱ sont des graphies de dur₁₁-ra "malade" (> /duru/ sous l'influence de l'harmonie vocalique et/ou suite à une réinterprétation); cf. Attinger, GSF 316 avec n. 756.

³³ V. la note à propos de du-ra = dur₁₁-ra.

³⁴ e₅ est une coquille.

³⁵ Delnero e = i-i, mais ga-e (VAT 1344 o. 9-11 = Cohen, Eršemma 33, VS 2, 72:9-11) peut fort bien recouvrir ga-i (ainsi par ex. Nuška B 4).

e-gal = e₂-gal: 581, 591; → nin-e-gal-la.
 e-ge-en = a-gen₇: 231, 269, 335:72, 544, 646.
 e-gi = a-gen₇: 265, 557, 624, 636.
 (*)e-gi = egi₂: 250, 531, 544, 546, 555, 556, 559, 591 sq.
 *e-gi-ir = egir: 258, 546, 622.
 e-ki-iš-nu-ĝal₂ = e₂-kiš-nu-ĝal₂: 559, 591.
^de-ki-ki = ^den-ki: 571.
 (^d)e-li-l = ^den-lil₂: 269, 531, 543, 609, 619, 623.
 e-lu-m = e-lum: 545, 591, 632.
 e-lu₂ = i-lu: 534, 633, 646.
 e-me = eme: 285, 571, 592, 632.
 e-me-da = ummeda: 550, 602.
 e-mi-da = emeda: 531, 592.
 e-mi-ga = ama-gan: 231, 339:85, 544, 646.
 e-ne = en₃: 531, 604.
 *e-nim = inim: 534, 595, 633.
 e-re = e-re₇: 559, 567, 580, 604, 615.
 *e-re-en = ^{ĝi}erⁱ: 257, 258, 263, 531, 592, 642.
 e-re-eš = ereš₃: 531, 592.
 e-ri = iri/eri³⁶: 540, 602, 636.
 e-ri = uru₂: 550, 602, 635.
 e-ri-b = e-rib: 531, 591.
 e-ri-n = ^{ĝe}erⁱ: 262, 531, 556, 592, 642, 649.
 e-ri-du = eridu^{ki}: 283, 571, 592.
 (*)e-ri-im = erim₂: 532, 592.
 e-ri-im = erim₃: 263, 532, 560, 592, 633.
 e-ri-im = ^{ĝe}erⁱ: 257, 263, 531, 592, 628, 642.
 e-ri-in = ^{ĝe}erⁱ: 263, 531, 592, 642.
 e-ri-i(š) = e-re₇: 567, 615.
 "e-si = ensi₂"³⁷: 257, 263, 531, 623, 632.
 e-si-r = e-sir₂: 571, 591.
 e-si-ir = e-sir₂: 552, 591.
 e-ya-na-aĝ₂ = a-na: 541, 611.
 e-ze₂-ra = ^diš^{ta}ran: 562, 648.
 e-zi-la = isla: 562, 595.
 e-zi-na-am = ^dezinam: 281, 571, 592.
 e-zi-na-ku-ru-si-ga = ^dezinam-^dku₃-su₃³⁸: 560, 647.
 e₂ = e₃: 559, 581.
 e₂ = e₄³⁹/a: 232, 544, 546, 559, 581.
 e₂-g = e-g/eg₂: 531, 580.
 e₂-n = en: → e₂-na-na.
 e₂-y: 233⁴⁰, 251, 327:36, 364, 542 (dans e₂(-)ya = (?) e₂-a), 611 (id.), 613.
 e₂-a-na = e₂-an-na: 531, 609, 625.
 e₂-a-tu-ub = a-eštub: 257, 528, 622.
 e₂-a-aš-tu-ub = a-eštub: 267, 557, 587, 631.
 e₂-di-n = edin: 546, 591.
 e₂-ge = a-gen₇: 528.
 e₂-gi = egi₂: 250, 555, 592.
 e₂-le-el = ^den-lil₂: 559, 623.
 e₂-lil₂(-na) = lil₂-la₂(-en-na): 233, 319:7, 319, 359, 548, 596.
 e₂-na-na = ^den-a₂-nun: 266, 531, 631, 646.
 e₂-sa-ra = e₂-SAR-ra: 559, 609.
 e₂-ya-na = e₂-an-na: 254, 559, 621.
 e₄-y: → a-y.

³⁶ Delnero uru.

³⁷ V. la critique justifiée de G. Marchesi dans MC 14 (2011) 109 n. 124.

³⁸ Ce n'est pas ku-ru(-)si-ga qui peut être une graphie non-standard de ^dku₃-su₃, mais tout au plus ku-ru. E. Bergmann (ZA 56 [1964] 25 sq.) rapproche avec hésitation l'expression de "guru₇-si-ga 'die Getreidehaufen auffüllt'", ce qui est assez tentant, d'autant plus que "guru₇" = kuru₁₃.

³⁹ e₅ est une coquille.

⁴⁰ Dans K₁ i 30' = SANER 26, 327:36, lire e₂-ya, pas e-ya (corriger en conséquence aussi les pp. 251, 364, 550 et 613).

eg = eg₂: 571.
 eġ₃(-...): → aġ₂(-...).
 el = il₂: 263, 534, 609, 633.
 el-de-eg = e^ġildag: 572, 595, 633.
 el-la = e^ġellaġ: 559, 592.
 *el-la-aġ₂ = e^ġellaġ: 559, 592.
 el-lu = i-lu: 48, 376, 416, 534, 633, 646.
 el-lu-um = e-lum: 567, 615.
 e(n) = e₄/a (dans en nu-na = e₄ nun-na): 575, 617.
 en = en₃: 546, 581.
 en = im₂: → de-el-en-babbar₂.
 en-a-nu-un = ^den-a₂-nun: 559, 592.
 en-gu-r = engur: 552, 592.
 *en-gu-ur = engur: 552, 592.
 *en-gur = engur: 552, 592.
 en-ni-in-nu-ra = en₂-e₂-nu-ru: 571, 592; → tu-ni-nu-ra.
 en-ša = en₃-ša₄: 560, 581.
 en-ša₄ = en₃-ša₄: 560, 581.
 en-še = en₃-še₃: 552, 560, 581.
 en-tar = en₃-tar: 323:21.
 er₂-si-ma⁴¹ = er₂-šem₅-ma: 480, 560, 609, 632, 644.
 eri-du₈ = eridu^{ki}: 571, 592.
 eš-ba-r = eš-bar: 546, 592.
 eš-dam = eš₃-dam: 553, 581.
 eš-de = aš-te: 256, 266, 267, 557, 628, 631, 632, 641.
 ga = gal: 560, 627, 637; → sur-ru-ga.
 ga-l = gal: 532, 546, 560, 604, 608, 627; → šu-ga-l, u₂-šu-ga-l.
 *ga-ab = gab₃: 546, 593, 625.
 ga-al = gal: → ga-al-la, i-ri-ga-al, ir-ra-ga-al, nu-ga-al.
 ga-al-ga = gal-gal: 254, 270, 560, 629.
 ga-al-ga-l = gal-gal: 254, 270, 560, 629.
 "ga-al-la = gal"⁴²: 254, 560, 629, 647.
 ga-az = gaz: 571, 593, 627, 629, 637.
 (*⁴³)ga-ba = gaba: 281 sq., 532, 550, 571, 593.
 ga-bu = gab₃(-bu): 532, 546, 571, 592, 625.
 ga-ka-az = gaz-gaz: 285, 571, 627, 629, 637.
 ga-na = gana₂: 286, 571, 593, 621, 627, 629, 637.
 ga-na-qa-na = gana₂-gana₂: 286, 571, 593, 621, 627, 629, 637.
 ga-ša = ga-ša-an: 261, 532, 542, 550, 567, 611, 613, 615, 623, 624, 637.
 ga-ša-n/n(a) = ga-ša-an: 261, 270, 532, 546, 593, 624, 637.
 ga-ša-an-an = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 560, 637, 647.
 ga-ša-an-di-lu-ba = ga-ša-an-tin-ugs₃-ba: 532, 560, 601.
 ga-ša-an-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 232, 268, 269, 270, 318:4, 532, 546, 560, 637, 647.
 ga-ša-an-na-an-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 344:99.
 ga-ša-an-na-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 232, 268, 269, 270, 546, 637, 647.
 ga-ša-an-ti-il-lu-ba = ga-ša-an-tin-ugs₃-ba: 560, 601.
 ga-ša-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 532, 637, 647.
 ga-ša-na-an = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 546, 550, 613, 637.
 ga-ša-na-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 532, 560, 637, 647.
 ga-te-eš = ka-teš₂: 285, 572, 638.
 gal-ga-al = gal-gal: 254, 270, 560, 629.
 ge = eġ₂: 543, 612.
 gi = gi₄: 232, 546, 581; → šu-ma-ar-gi.
 gi = gi₄-in: 567, 615.
 gi = gig: 283, 286.
 "gi = ġi₆": 533, 643⁴³.
 gi-b = gub: 232, 334:69, 546, 631, 648.
 gi-d = gid₂: 546, 560, 604 sq.

⁴¹ Inconsequent avec la lecture ir₂ de A.IGI dans le reste de l'ouvrage.

⁴² Dans X₄₆ (= PBS 10/2, 13 = Bergmann, ZA 56, 13 sqq.) f. 6', on a ga-al, pas ga-al-la.

⁴³ Dans VAT 608 + o. i 22, 25 (= Sjöberg, JCS 34, 74 16' B 22 et 18' B 25, on a saġ-ge-ge = saġ-gege/geg₂-ga.

gi-g = gīg: → gi-g(a).
 gi-r = egir: → gi-r(e).
 gi-y = gi₄: 322:17.
 gi-g(a) = gīg(-ga): 261, 282, 560, 572, 605, 638, 121.
 gi-gi = gi₄-gi₄: 532, 581.
 gi-gi = geg₂-ga⁴⁴: 561, 581, 643.
 gi-gi-r = ^{gi₅}gigir: 532, 593.
 *gi-gi-ir = ^{gi₅}gigir: 532, 593.
 gi-gi-lu = gi₁₆-gi₁₆-le: 546, 550, 581, 613.
 gi-gi-ru-m = GAM.GAM: 345:102,373 sq.
 gi-gu-na = gi-gun₄-na: 251, 546, 609.
 gi-gu-ru-m = gigurum: 232, 546, 593.
 gi-gu₂-na = gi-gun₄-na: 252, 560, 609.
 gi-iĝ₃ = gi-in: 255, 560, 626, 628, 643.
 gi-ir = kiri₃⁴⁵: 535, 595, 639.
 gi-ir-gi-r(e) = gi₄-gi₄⁴⁶: 560, 629, 638.
 gi-ir-za-al = kiri₃-zal: 562, 576, 596, 639.
 gi-ki-ga = gegge-ga: → sa-gi-ki-ga.
 gi-le(-ĝ) = gi-le-eĝ₃: 532, 609, 643.
 gi-le(-ĝ) = gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: 232, 263, 268, 321:14, 546, 560, 593, 643, 647.
 gi-le-^reĝ₃⁴⁷ = gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: 263, 268, 560, 593, 643.
 gi-le-em = gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: 263, 268, 560, 593, 643; → na-gi-le-em.
 gi-li = kilim: → ni-in-gi-li.
 gi-li-li = kilim: → niĝ₂-gi-li-li.
 (g)i-maš = amaš⁴⁷: 568, 616.
 gi-qa-r = ^{gi₅}gigir: 329:47.
 gi-qa-ir = ^{gi₅}gigir: 232, 234, 329:47, 546, 551, 619, 621, 627, 638.
 gi-r(e) = egir: 232, 233, 234, 258, 328:41, 365, 546, 550, 551, 613, 622.
 (*)gi-ri = kiri₃: 535, 595 sq., 639.
 gi-ri-in = gi-rin: 532, 593.
 gi-ri-lu^{se-en} = gir-gi₄-lu^{mušen}: 546, 648.
 gi-ru = gurum: 232, 259, 546, 593, 646.
 gi-sa = gi₁₆-sa: 560, 581.
 gi-zi-la = gi-izi-la₂: 571.
 gi₄-g(a) = gīg(-ga): 261, 282, 560, 605, 638.
 gi₄-gi₄ = gīg-gīg: 286.
 gi₄-ku-na = gi-gun₄-na: 251, 553, 609, 627, 638.
 gīg = gi₄-gi₄: 286, 571, 629, 638.
 gīg-gīg = gi₄-gi₄: 286, 571, 629, 638.
 gir-zal = kiri₃-zal: 547, 639, 648.
 gu = gu₂: 249 sq., 269, 533, 560, 572, 581.
 gu = gu₃: 533, 581.
 gu = gu₄: 560, 572, 581.
 gu = gur⁴⁸: 533, 638.
 (*)gu = ku₂: 262, 535, 562, 568, 583, 616, 639.
 gu-b = gub: 533, 561, 605.
 gu-l = gul: 251, 261, 533, 561, 605, 609, 638.
 gu-r = gur: 533, 546, 605, 609, 638.
 gu-gu-ub = gub-gub: 254, 561, 629.
 gu-ku-l = gakkul: 571.
 gu-li = ku-li: 562, 583, 639.
 (*)gu-nu = gun₃: 533, 572, 593, 605.
 *gu-u₂ = ku₂: 262, 535, 583.
 (*)gu-ub = gub: 533, 555, 561, 593, 605.

⁴⁴ Delnero = ĝi₆ (il confond dans tout l'ouvrage ĝe₆ "nuit" et ge₆/geg₂/gegge-g "noir"); X₅₂ o. ii 7 = Alster, ASJ 14, 10:40.

⁴⁵ Delnero lit dans tout l'ouvrage kiri₄.

⁴⁶ Le sens de X₅₃ o. 13 = Limet, Akkadica 117, 4/18:13 m'échappe, mais gi-ir-gi-r(e) ne peut guère recouvrir gi₄-gi₄ (à moins qu'on ait affaire à gi₍₄₎-r "cogner", ce qui semble invraisemblable dans le contexte). Limet (op. cit. 7) envisage une graphie de gir₅-gir₅, mais ne traduit pas le passage.

⁴⁷ Dans niĝ₂(-)-gi-maš = niĝ₂ amaš.

⁴⁸ Dans a gu a gu = a₂ gur a₂ gur.

gu-ub-gub = gub-gub: 254, 561, 629.
 (*)gu-ul = gul: 180:103, 261 sq., 345 sq. l. 103, 533, 561, 593, 605, 638.
 gu-ul-gu-ul = gul-gul: 261 sq., 284, 555, 561, 572, 593, 629, 630, 638.
 gu-um-gu-um = gum-gum: 533, 629.
 gu-un-gu-nu = gun₃-gun₃: 561, 629, 638.
 *gu-ur = gur: 275.
 gu-ur = kur₂: 576, 639.
 gu-ur-gu-r = gur-gur: 533, 629, 638.
 gu₂ = gu₃: 232, 233, 251, 343:98, 546, 550, 575, 581, 613, 617.
 (*)gu₂ = ku₂: 232, 262, 535, 547, 562, 583, 639.
 gu₂ = ugu: → ama-gu₂.
 *gu₂-u₂ = ku₂: 262, 535, 583, 639.
 gu₄ = gu₂: 250, 269, 533, 546, 581.
 gu₄-ul-gu₄-ul = gul-gul: 576, 593, 629, 638.
 gul-UL = gul-gul: 102, 318, 546, 638.
 gup-p = gub: 285, 572, 628, 640.
 gur = gur₃: 533, 581.
 gur-u₃ = gur₃-ru: 251, 293, 536, 542, 597, 612, 636, 642.
 gurus-ru = gigurum: 560, 648.
 ĝa₂ = ĝal₂: → a-nu-ĝa₂.
 (ĝ)a₂-k = AK: → niĝ₂-ĝa₂-ka.
 ĝa₂-l = ĝal₂: 533, 553, 605, 609; → ħe-ĝa₂-l, ħu-lu-ĝa₂-l, ħu-ur-ĝa₂-l, ku-ĝa₂-l.
 ĝa₂-n = ĝin: 232, 271, 340:88, 547, 631.
 ĝa₂-r = ĝar: 232, 533, 547, 553, 561, 605, 609.
 ĝa₂-al = ĝal₂: 533, 553, 561, 593 sq.; → ħe-ĝa₂-al, i-ri-ĝa₂-al, ni-zi-ĝa₂-al.
 ĝa₂-ar = ĝar: 533, 594; → al-ĝa₂-ar-sur-ra.
 ĝa₂-ar-^udu^u = ^umar-tu: 553, 597.
 ĝa₂-nu-ma-aĥ = ĝa₂-nun-maĥ: 546, 551, 613, 648.
 ĝa₂-ri⁴⁹ = me-ri (ES pour ĝiri₃): 232, 319:11, 547, 648.
 (ĝ)e₆ = e₂: 279:3, 568, 616.
 *ĝe₆-en = ĝin/ĝen⁵⁰: 561, 594.
 *ĝe₆-eš-tu⁵¹ = ĝeštu₂: 594, 643.
 ĝi₆⁵² = ĝin: 258, 533, 561, 594, 605, 609, 624, 643.
 ĝi₆-n/mi-n = ĝin: 561, 594, 605, 609, 643⁵³.
 ĝi₆-ba-r = ĝi₆-par₃: 553, 594, 640.
 ĝi₆-ĝu₁₀-na = ĝi₆-u₃-na⁵⁴: 561, 648.
 ĝi₆-in = ĝin: 561, 594.
 ĝi₆-iš = ĝi₆⁵⁵: 572, 594, 635, 643.
 ĝi₆-pa-r = ĝi₆-par₃: 572, 594.
 (ĝi)n = an (dans nu-ĝin-na = nu-gig an-na): 568, 616.
 ĝir₃ = ĝir₂: 572, 581.
 ĝiri₂ = ĝiri₃: 232.
 ĝi₆š = ĝi₆š₃: 561, 582.
 ĝi₆š-ĥu-ur₂ = ĝi₆š-ĥur: 533, 594.
 ĝi₆š-nu = ĝi₆š-nu₂: 561, 582.
 ĝ(u₁₀) = aĝ₂: 578, 618.
 (ĝ)u₁₀ = ur₂: 568, 616; → ne-ĝu₁₀-li-mu.
 ĥa-al-ĥa-al = ⁱ⁷ĥal-ĥal: 572, 594.
 ĥa-am-bu-r = ĥenbur₂: 572, 594.
 ĥa-an-du-ur-sa-ĝa₂ = ^uĥendur-saĝ-ĝa₂: 265, 561, 594, 636.
 *ĥa-aš-ĥu-ur = ^{ĝi6}ĥašĥur: 547, 594, 623.

⁴⁹ Mieux ĝe₂₆-ri?

⁵⁰ Delnero ĝi₆-en = ĝin; correct est naturellement ĝe₆-en = ĝen.

⁵¹ Delnero mi-eš-tu.

⁵² Delnero oscille entre ĝi₆ et mi.

⁵³ Delnero transcrit MI-na dans BM 78175 (= CT 44, 12; cf. CLAM 47 et 52 sqq.) tantôt ĝi₆-na tantôt mi-na. Comme le texte est en ES, on attendrait /men/.

⁵⁴ On voit en général dans MI.MU-na la forme ES correspondant à ĝe₆-u₃-na (attendu serait toutefois */meuna/); sur MI.MU-na, cf. Schretter, *Emesal-Studien* (1990) 216 sq. avec litt. ant. et J. Bauer, *Or.* 81 (2012) 251; sur la passage, cf. M. Jaques, *OBO* 273 (2015) 218:1 (comm. p. 219).

⁵⁵ Dans ĝi₆-iš te-e-ra = ĝi₆š ter-ra "arbres du bosquet". La translittération ĝi₆-iš-te-e-ra = ĝi₆š-ter-ra de Delnero donne l'impression erronée que l'on a affaire à ^{ĝe6}ter "bosquet, forêt".

ɥa-aš-ɥu-ur₂ = ^{ɛ̃is}ɥašɥur: 283, 286, 561, 594, 623.
 ɥa-aš-ku-r = ^{ɛ̃is}ɥašɥur: 283, 561, 594, 623, 646.
 ɥa-aš₂-ɥu-r = ^{ɛ̃is}ɥašɥur⁵⁶: 286, 572, 594, 623.
 *ɥa-aš₂-ɥu-ur = ^{ɛ̃is}ɥašɥur: 547, 594, 623.
 ɥa-ɥa-al = ɥal-ɥal: 561, 630.
 ɥa-la-m = ɥa-lam: 561, 594.
 ɥa-mu-n = ɥa-mun: 572, 594.
 ɥa-ra-n = ɥar-ra-an: 232, 251, 329:47, 533, 547, 609, 625.
 ɥa-šu-r = ^{ɛ̃is}ɥašɥur: 283, 286, 533, 547, 572, 594, 623.
 ɥa-šu-r = ɥa-šu-ur₂: 533, 623.
 ɥar-ra-n = ɥar-ra-an: 366, 578, 609.
 *ɥe-en-du-ur-saĝ = ^dɥendur-saĝ-ĝa₂: 265, 561, 594, 636.
 ɥe-ĝa₂-l = ɥe₂-ĝal₂: 533, 582, 594.
 ɥe-ĝa₂-al = ɥe₂-ĝal₂: 572, 594.
 ɥe-ĝal₂ = ɥe₂-ĝal₂: 533, 576, 582.
 ɥe₂-du₁₀ = ɥe₂-du₇: 553, 582.
^mɥi-bu-ur₂ = ^{ɛ̃i}ɥenbur: 533, 594, 623.
 ɥi-ir = ɥir: 572, 594.
 ɥi-iš = ɥeš₅: 561, 594, 633.
 ɥu-ĝ = ɥuĝ⁵⁷: 534, 542, 547, 553, 561, 605, 611, 628, 643.
 ɥu-l = ɥul: 534, 553, 561, 605, 629.
 ɥu-l = ɥul₂: 534, 547, 553, 561, 605, 609.
 ɥu-š = ɥuš: 576, 606.
 ɥu-bu-r = ɥu-bu-ur₂: 547, 594.
 ɥu-bur = ɥu-bu-ur₂: 547, 594.
 ɥu-ɥu = ɥUL.ɥUL: 232, 254, 320:12 sq., 547, 630.
 ɥu-la-ɥu-la = ɥul₂-la-ɥul₂-la⁵⁸: 534, 630.
 (*)ɥu-lu = ɥul: 270, 435, 534, 547, 553, 594, 605, 609, 629; → ni-im-ɥu-lu-di-ma, niĝ₂-ɥu-lu-di-ma.
 ɥu-lu-ɥ = ɥu-luɥ: 533, 561, 594.
 ɥu-lu-ĝa₂-l = ɥul-ĝal₂: 104:4' sq.
 ɥu-lu-ub = ^{ɛ̃is}ɥa-lu-ub₂: 266, 553, 555, 620, 631.
 ɥu-saĝ = ɥur-saĝ: 258, 534, 623.
 (*)ɥu-ul = ɥul: 534, 553, 572, 594, 629.
 (*)ɥu-ul = ɥul₂: 534, 553, 595.
 ɥu-ul-ɥu-ul = ɥUL.ɥUL: 254, 320:12, 561, 572, 594, 630.
 *ɥu-un = ɥun: 534, 606, 644.
 ɥu-un-ĝal₂ = ɥul-ĝal₂: 572.
 ɥu-ur = ɥur: → ni-iš-ɥu-ur.
 ɥu-ur-ĝa₂-l = ɥul-ĝal₂: 576.
 ɥu-ur-su-g = ɥur-saĝ: → niĝ₂-ɥu-ur-su-ga.
 ɥu-ur₂ = ɥur: → ĝiš-ɥu-ur₂.
 ɥu-ur₂-sa₂-ĝ = ɥur-saĝ⁵⁹: 534, 561, 595, 644.
 ɥu-uš = ɥuš: 572, 595.
 ɥul = ɥul₂: 327:34.
 ɥul-lu = ɥul: 149 sq. ll. 3-8, 197:4-9, 270, 458, 547, 605.
 ɥul-ɥu-lu = ɥUL.ɥUL: 320:12 sq.
 ɥul-lu-ɥul-l = ɥUL.ɥUL: 254, 534, 630.
 ɥur-sa-ĝ = ɥur-saĝ: 547, 595.
 (*)i = i₃: 274, 561, 582.
 (*)i(-d) = i₇: 232, 534, 547, 561, 572, 582, 625.
 i-l = il₂: 251, 263, 534, 547, 553, 561, 606, 609, 633.
 i-n = en⁶⁰: 283 (dans i-ni-in-ki-id-ki/i-ni-in-ki-ki = en ^den-ki-ke⁶¹), 575 (id.), 617.
 i-r = ir₂: 234:25', 251, 271, 347:105, 534, 547, 551, 553, 555, 562, 606, 609, 613, 633; v. i-še še-še.
 i-bi = i-bi₂: 87:15 (dans i-bi-te-en), 94:8', 232, 345:101, 350:111, 374, CBS 106:5', 534, 547, 555, 561, 582, 614.

⁵⁶ ɥasur (pp. 202, 547, 561, 594, 623, 646) est une coquille pour ɥašɥur.

⁵⁷ Dans -ɥu-MI = -ɥu-ĝe₂₆, etc.; Delnero oscille entre ɥu-mi = ɥun, ɥu-mi = ɥun-e et ɥu-ĝi₆ = ɥun.

⁵⁸ Ainsy Delnero probabl. à juste titre; d'après M. Jaques (OBO 273 [2015] 45/46:24'), ɥu-la-ɥu-la est une graphie de ɥul(u)-a-ɥul(u)-a.

⁵⁹ Au lieu de ɥu-ur₂-sa₂-ĝe₉, Delnero lit ɥu-ur₂-sa₂-ni₅ (561, 595, 644).

⁶⁰ Mais v. Attinger, GSF 347 n. 854.

⁶¹ Mais v. ma critique dans GSF 347 n. 854.

(*)i-gi = igi: 282, 534, 561, 572, 595.
 i-ik-še = keš₂: 572, 595.
 i-ig-la = ¹⁷idigna: 572.
 i-ma-š = amaš (mieux e₂-maš): 265, 267, 552, 636, 644.
 i-ma-al = im-ma-al: 251, 561, 609.
 i-me = eme: 285, 571, 592, 632.
 i-ne-eĝ₃ = e-ne-eĝ₃: 268, 531, 632.
 i-ni = e-ne: 559, 576, 632.
 i-ni = e-ne-eĝ₃: 568, 615.
 i-ni-ĝ = e-ne-eĝ₃: 268, 269, 559, 591, 632.
 i-ni-k = e-ne-eĝ₃: 268, 269, 559, 591, 632.
 i-ni-m = e-ne-eĝ₃⁶²: 268, 269, 445, 559, 568, 591, 615, 632.
 i-ni-m = inim: → ka-i-ni-ma.
 i-ni-ĝar = inim-ĝar⁶³: 268, 534, 542, 595, 611, 633.
 i-ni-im = e-ne-eĝ₃⁶⁴: 268, 559, 591, 632.
 i-ni-im = inim: 534, 595, 633.
 *i-nim = inim: 534, 595, 633.
 *i-ri = iri/eri⁶⁵: 540, 602, 636.
 i-ri-m = erim₂: 546, 592, 632.
 i-ri-ga-al = iri₁₁-gal: 562, 595, 636.
 i-ri-ĝa₂-al = erim₂-ĝa₂: 577, 618.
 i-ri-im = erim₂: 576, 592, 632.
 *i-ri-im-ma = erim₃: 263, 546, 592⁶⁶, 633.
 i-ri-ma = erim₃: 232, 263, 352-353:118, 546, 553, 592, 632.
 i-si-n = i₃-si-in^{ki}: 269, 534, 560, 582, 609, 625.
 i-si-in^{ki} = i₃-si-in^{ki}: 534, 582.
 i-si-š(i) = i-si-iš: 561, 595, 646.
 i-še še-še = ir₂-še₃ še₂₂-še₂₂: 347:105.
 i-ti = iti₆: 553, 595.
 i-ti-d = iti₆⁶⁷: 534, 595.
 i-tu-ub = i-dub⁶⁸: 572, 641.
 i-ya = na₄: 254, 563, 621.
 i-zi = izi: 572, 595.
 i₃-r = ir₂: 252, 553, 606, 609, 633.
 i₃-lu = ilu: 582, 651.
 i₃-si-n = i₃-si-in^{ki}: 269, 534, 560, 582, 609, 625.
 *ib = ib₂: 275.
 (i)b-la = bala: → ki-ib-la.
 (i)b-l(e) = bala-e (dans -ti-ib-le = -ti-ib-ba-la-e): 283, 575, 618.
 (i)b-ru = buru₄: → ki-ib-ru.
 id = i₇-d: 232, 234, 255, 329:46, 366, 547, 551, 572, 582, 613, 625.
 (i)g-na-ĝ = (?) ka-na-aĝ₂ (dans ši ig-na-^rĝa₂⁷⁹): 569, 616.
 (i)g-ru = gur₃-ru: 577.
 igi du = igi du₈: 345:101.
 igi-na-ma = igi-nim-ma: 251, 554, 614.
 (i)k-še = keš₂: 572, 595.
 il = il₂: 547, 561, 582.
 (i)l-la = la₂: 575, 617.
 il-lil₂ = il₂-il₂: 234, 551, 613, 630.
 il-tu-ub = ildum₂: 561, 641.
 il₂-lil₂ = il₂-il₂: 232, 547, 630.
 im = im₂: 578, 582.
 im-ma = imma₃: → ni-in-ni-in-ma.

⁶² Même en contexte ES, une forme EG (= inim) est aussi envisageable.

⁶³ Rangé partiellement s.v. R = e-ne-eĝ₃.

⁶⁴ Même en contexte ES, une forme EG (= inim) est aussi envisageable.

⁶⁵ Delnero uru.

⁶⁶ i-ri-im-ma est la glose à "erim₃", pas à erim₂.

⁶⁷ Ainsi Delnero, mais iti₆ a une finale vocalique (Attinger, GSF 582 avec n. 1632); on a plutôt affaire à iti-d "mois".

⁶⁸ Delnero i₃-dub.

im-si = ensi⁶⁹: 560, 632.
 in = en: 576, 632.
 in-da = ninda: 251, 272, 273, 568, 616.
 in-da-ag-ra = ^dindag(a)ra⁷⁰: 562, 595.
 in-ki-k = ^den-ki-k⁷¹: 283, 575, 617.
 in-si = ensi²: 263⁷², 531, 560, 576, 592, 632.
 ir = ir₂: 232, 239:14', 534, 547, 555, 562, 582, 606, 633.
 ir-ra-ga-al = ^dir₃-ra-gal: 562, 595.
 ir-ša-ni-ša = ir₂-ša₃-ne-ša₄: 562, 595, 633.
 ir-ši še-še = ir₂-še₃ še₂₂-še₂₂: 347:105.
 ir ši-ši = ir₂ še₂₂-še₂₂: 239:14'.
 ir₂ = ir₉: 562, 582.
 iš-gar₃ = ^munus-aš₂-gar₃: 283, 570, 589.
 išib-gal = ušumgal: → am-išib-gal-an-na.
 (i)t-ku-r = tukur₂: 285, 574, 575, 617, 622.
 (i)t-tu = du₃: 578, 618.
 (k)a = an (ciel): 567 (dans bu-lu-ka-ki), 615 (id.).
 *ka = ka₂: 562, 644, 648.
 ka = kaš (dans ka-ši = kaš-še₃)⁷³: 275, 534, 542, 606, 612.
 ka-ĝ = ka-na-aĝ₂: 268, 562, 595, 644.
 ka-s = kas₄: 534, 606, 644.
 *ka-ab = gab₃: 546, 593, 625.
 ka-aĝ₂-ka-an = KA₂: 257, 562, 628, 644, 648.
 ka-al = kal: 572, 595.
 ka-am-ka-am = gam-gam^{mušen}: 285, 571, 627, 629, 637.
 *ka-an-ka-an = KA₂: 257, 562, 628, 644, 648.
 ka-ar = kar: 562, 595.
 (*)ka-aš = kaš: 275, 534, 562, 595.
 *ka-aš₂ = kas₄: 534, 606, 644.
 ka-ĝa₂ = ka-na-aĝ₂ (dans ka-ĝa₂-ka = ka-na(-aĝ₂)-ĝa₂-ka): 268, 562, 595, 644.
 ka-i-ni-ma = ka-inim-ma: 572, 595.
 ka-ki-d = kar-kid₂: 283, 575, 617.
 ka-la-ak-ka = kalag-ga: 576, 627, 639.
 ka-la-am = kalam: 534, 595.
 ka-na = ka-na-aĝ₂: 568, 616.
 ka-na-ĝ = ka-na-aĝ₂: 268, 534, 562, 595, 644.
 ka-na-m = ka-na-aĝ₂: 268, 534, 644.
 ka-na-m = kalam: 576, 595.
 ka-na-am = ka-na-aĝ₂: 268, 534, 644.
 ka-nam = ka-na-aĝ₂: 268, 534, 644.
 ka-ša = ga-ša-an: 261, 532, 542, 560, 568, 612, 616, 624, 627.
 ka-ša-n = ga-ša-an: 261, 532, 612, 624, 627, 637.
 ka-ša-aĝ₂-na-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 269, 560, 627, 637, 647.
 ka-ša-an = ga-ša-an: 261, 532, 546, 555, 556, 560, 624, 626 sq., 637.
 ka-ša-an-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 532, 555, 568, 616, 627, 637, 647.
 ka-ša-an-na-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 269, 532, 560, 627, 637, 647.
 ka-ša-na-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 269, 270, 532, 546, 568, 616, 627, 637, 647.
 ka-ta-ar = ka-tar: 539, 600.
 ke = AK: 528, 579.
 ke-eš = keš₃^{ki}: 255, 534, 543, 606, 619, 625.
 keš = keš₃^{ki}: 542, 612, 625.
 ki = gi (jeune femme): 256, 546, 627, 638.

⁶⁹ Sic, pas im-si-na = ensi(m) (Delnero). Le sens du na-še₃ (// ma-še₃?) qui suit n'est pas clair, mais comme il ressort de la ligne suivante (a-ra sa¹²-še₃ // a-ra ša₃-še₃ // a-ra na-še₃?), il n'est pas un constituant du lexème. Sur ce passage, cf. A. Cavigneaux, ASJ 18 (1996) 33.

⁷⁰ Delnero enregistre in-da-ak-ra s.v. ^dindak et doit donc voir dans -ra un datif. Dans X₄₆ (= PBS 10/2, 13 = Bergmann, ZA 56, 13 sqq.) f. 3, un datif n'entre pas en considération. Une nouvelle attestation de in-da-ag-ra est George, CUSAS 32 n° 24 rev. 3' (cf. p. 116).

⁷¹ Mais v. Attinger, GSF 347 n. 854.

⁷² Dans VAT 604+ r. (= VS 2, 3) iii, 6, 9, on a u₃-mu-un-in-si, graphie non-standard de u₃-mu-un-si, ES pour ensi₂.

⁷³ Ainsi Delnero 542 et 612. Remarquer toutefois que dans ka-ši ga-na-su-ur₂ (= sur) (VAT 615+ = VS 2, 31 i 9'), on n'attend pas de terminatif.

ki = gi (roseau): → ne₂-eš-ki.
 ki = gi₄: 560, 627, 638.
 ki-d = kid₂: → ka-ki-d.
 ki-g = gig: → ki-g(a).
 ki-š = kiš^{ki}: 547, 606.
 ki-ba-la = ki-bala: 572, 595.
 ki-en-gi₄ = kin-gi₄: 562, 648.
 ki-g(a) = gig(-ga): 261, 282, 560, 605, 627, 638.
 ki-ga-aĝ₂ = ki-aĝ₂: 342:95, 343:[9]7.
 ki-gi = gi₄-gi₄: 286, 571, 627, 629, 638.
 ki-gi = ki-gig: 283, 575, 617.
 ki-gi-k = "ĝi⁶"⁷⁴: → saĝ-ki-gi-ki-ak.
 ki-gig = gi₄-gi₄: 286, 571, 627, 629, 638.
 ki-i₃-ki⁷⁵ = ki-en-gi: 577, 618.
 ki-ib-la = ki-bala: 576, 622.
 ki-ib-ru = ki-buru₁₄: 575, 617.
 ki-in-gi-r = ki-en-gi-r: 267, 534, 631.
 ki-ir = kiri₆: 535, 596.
 ki-is₃-ki-r = ki-sikil: 285, 573, 622.
 ki-iš-ke-el = ki-sikil: 232, 234, 258, 263, 285, 327:34, 547, 551, 613, 622, 633, 644.
 ki-iš-ki-il = ki-sikil: 258, 263, 285, 562, 622, 633.
 ki-iš-ki-il₂ = ki-sikil: 258, 263, 285, 547, 622, 633, 644.
 ki-ki-ši-d = keš₂-keš₂-d: 284, 572, 595, 630, 639.
 *ki-ri = kiri₃: 535, 596, 639.
 ki-ri = kiri₆: 535, 562, 573, 596.
 ki-sa-l = kisal: 250, 535, 596.
 *ki-sa-al = kisal: 535, 596.
 ki-sa₂-al = kisal: 250, 535, 596.
 ki-si-ki = ki-sikil: 263, 562, 622, 624, 633.
 ki-si-qa = ki-si₃-ga: 284, 572, 621, 627, 639.
 ki-še = kiši₈: 573, 596.
 ki-ši = keš₂: 572, 595, 639.
 *ki-te = gidim: 560, 593, 627, 638.
 *ki-ti = gidim: 560, 593, 627, 638.
 (*ki-ti-im = gidim: 282, 560, 571, 593, 627, 638.
 *ki-tim = gidim: 560, 593, 627, 638.
 ki-tu-š = ki-tuš: 269, 535, 606, 625, 631.
 ki-tu-uš = ki-tuš: 103:70, 334:70.
 ki-u₃-r = ki-ur₃: 535, 542, 609, 612.
 ki-ur = ki-ur₃: 562, 583.
 ku = ku⁷⁶: 262, 535, 562, 583, 639.
 ku(-g) = ku₃: 233, 275, 345-346:102 sq., 535, 547, 562, 573, 583.
 (*ku = ku₅: 556, 583; → di-ku.
 (k)u = u₂: 543, 612.
 ku-d = ku₅-d: 535, 583.
 ku-k = ku₃-g: 275, 562, 583.
 ku-l = gul: 251, 261, 533, 553, 555, 561, 605, 609, 627, 638.
 ku-r = ku₅: 562, 583.
 ku-r = kur: 535, 547, 562, 596, 606, 609.
 ku-r = kur₂: 562, 606, 609.
 ku-š = kuš₂: 240:25' sq., 535, 596.
 ku-t = ku₅-d: 286, 535, 573, 575, 583, 617, 642.
 ku-ĝa₂-l = ku₃-ĝal₂: 233, 352:116, 547, 596.
 ku-ku = ku₄-ku₄: 577, 618.
 ku-kur = kurku₂: 535, 596.
 ku-la-ab = kul-aba^{ki}: 553, 596.
 ku-la-ba = kul-aba^{ki}: 547, 551, 596, 619.
 ku-nu = gun₃: 556, 593, 627, 638.

⁷⁴ En fait gegge-g.

⁷⁵ Delnero ki-ni-ki.

⁷⁶ Delnero translittère normalement KU₂ ku₂, mais une fois gu₇ (p. 627, à propos de ku = gu₇!).

ku-ru-m = gurum: 572, 593, 627, 638.
 ku-ru-uš = ġuruš: 553, 594, 643.
 ku-su = ^dku₃-su₃: 283, 573, 583, 596.
 ku-tu-uš = ki-tuš: 266, 535, 542, 612, 625, 631.
 *ku-u₂ = ku₃: 275, 583.
 *ku-u₂ = ku₅: 535, 583.
 ku-u₄-gu-r = kur-kur: 562, 606⁷⁷.
 ku-uk = ku₃-k⁷⁸: 573, 583.
 ku-ul(-ku-ul) = gul(-gul): 261 sq., 284, 553, 593, 627, 629, 638.
 ku-ul-la-ba = kul-aba^{ki}: 562, 596.
 ku-un = kun: 573, 596.
 ku-ur = kur: 573, 596.
 ku-ur-ku = kurku₂: 562, 596.
 ku-ur₂ = kur: 547, 596.
 ku-ur₂-ku = kurku₂: 535, 596.
 ku-ur₂-ku-r = gur-gur: 533(?), 553, 627, 629(?), 638.
 ku-us₂-su = ^dku₃-su₃: 573, 583.
 ku-zu = ku₃-zu: 535, 583.
 ku₃-ġa₂-ra = kur-ġar-ra: 535, 623.
 kur = kur₂: 562, 573, 583, 606.
 *kur = kur₄: 274.
 kur-ġa₂-ra = kur-ġar-ra: 562, 596, 623.
 kur-ku = kurku₂: 535, 596.
 kur-ku-r = kur-kur: 576.
 kur-kur = ku₄-ku₄: 535, 630⁷⁹.
 kur-kur = kurku₂: 547, 562, 596.
 la = la₂: 250, 535, 548, 556, 562, 573, 583; → gi-zi-la, su-um-la-su-la, u₃-nu la, zu-bi₂ la.
 la = lu (dans la-am₃): 578, 618.
 la-ḥ = laḥ₄: 228, 229, 233, 319:11, 360, 535, 548, 562, 596, 606.
 (I)a-n = an; → a-ma-u₂-šu-ga-la-na, ama-šu-ga-la-na, ama-šu-gal-la-na, ama-šu-mu-gal-la-na, ama-u₃-šu-gal-la-na.
 *la-aḥ = laḥ₄: 535, 596, 606.
 la-al = la₃: 535, 596.
 la-ga-s = lagaš^{ki}: 535, 596, 644.
 la-ra-g = la-ra-ak^{ki80}: 535, 639.
 la-ra-g = la₇-ra₃⁸¹-ak^{ki}: 562, 569, 596, 620, 639.
 la₂-la₂ = lam-lam: 562, 630.
 le = la₂-e: 550, 613.
 li-l = lib: 327:35 (comm. p. 363 sq.).
 li-l = lib₂: 535, 548, 596, 609; → ^de-li-l.
 li-bi-r = li-bi-ir: 553, 596.
 *li-il = lil₂: 563.
 li-mu = limmu₂: → ne-ġu₁₀-li-mu.
 lu = ḥul (dans u₄-lu = u₄ ḥul): 234, 329:58, 551, 614.
 lu = lu₂: 233, 271, 548, 573, 576, 583; → a-sa-al-lu-ḥi.
 lu = ulu₃: → lu-lu.
 lu-l = lul: 536, 562, 606, 609.
 lu-ga-l = lugal: → na-lu-ga-l.
 lu-li-im = lu-lim: 240:24', 562, 596.
 *lu-li-im = lulim: 562, 596.
 *lu-lim = lulim: 562, 596.
 lu-lu = lu₂-ulu₃⁸²: 283, 573, 575, 617, 648; → na-aġ₂-lu-lu.
 lu-lu = lu₃-lu₃: 562, 583.
 lu-lu-um = lum-lum: 562, 630.
 lu₂-ga-l = lugal: 242:22', 250, 535, 542 (lu₂-ga-[...]), 596.

⁷⁷ Ainsi CLAM 204:4 et copie p. 822 (R-ra); Delnero translittère ku-u₄-ku-⁷x⁷-ra (sur collation?).

⁷⁸ Dans ku-uk ki-a = ku₃ ki-a; cf. A. Cavigneaux, ASJ 17 (1995) 78/81:4 A et comm. p. 84.

⁷⁹ Lire VAT 613+ (= VS 2, 4) ii 28'-29' (cf. Cohen, Eršemma 130 n° 34.1:8 sq.).

⁸⁰ La distinction fait entre la-ra-ak^{ki} et la₇-ra₃-ak^{ki} m'échappe.

⁸¹ -ra₂- (Delnero) est une coquille.

⁸² Sic, pas -ulu₂.

lu₂-gal = lugal: 250, 251, 535, 541, 562, 576, 596, 611.
 lu₂-gi-b = mu-gi₁₇-ib: 270, 548, 642, 646, 648.
 lu₂-lu = lu₂-ulu₃: 573, 648.
 lu₂-lu₂ = lu₂-ulu₃: 535, 553, 625, 648; → nam-lu₂-lu₂.
 lu₂-lu₂(-u₄) = lu₂-ulu₃ (dans lu₂-lu₂-u₄-ra): 548, 648.
 lul-la = lu₃-lu₃⁸³: 562, 583.
 lum = e-lum: 258, 552, 622.
 ma = ama: 550, 613.
 ma = ma-al: 536, 624.
 ma = ^ēes₃ma₂: 233, 536, 551, 548, 583, 619.
 ma = mu₂: 568, 616.
 ma-ḥ = maḥ: 536, 567, 573, 576, 606, 614; → ur₂-ma-ḥ.
 ma-l = ma-al: 548, 563, 596, 615.
 (m)a-n = an: 283, 575, 617.
 ma-r = mar: 548, 563, 606, 609.
 ma-s = amaš: 251, 258, 267, 270, 528, 544, 554, 588, 614, 622, 644.
 (*)ma-aḥ = maḥ: 536, 548, 597, 606; → ḡa₂-nu-ma-aḥ.
 ma-ar = mar: → šu-ma-ar-gi.
 ma-aš = muš₃: 266, 556, 636.
 ma-gI-ur = mu-un-gur₁₁: 328:37.
 ma-gu-ur₅ = ^ēis₃ma₂-gur₈: 252, 548, 551, 597, 619.
 ma-nu-n = ma-nun: 563, 609.
 (m)a-še-[...] = a-še-er: 550, 613.
 ma-tu = ma₂-du₃: 329:46 (cf. comm. p. 366).
 ma-ya = ma-a-a: 238:5' sq., 254, 536, 621.
 ma₂ = ama: 366.
 maḥ-ti = maḥ-di: 548, 642.
 maš-a-ši = maš₂-anše: 257, 529, 557, 623.
 maš-gi-in = maškim: 536, 597, 639.
 ma₂-s = amaš: 258, 267, 270, 544, 588, 622, 644.
 (m)e = e₃: 541, 611.
 (*)me = me-e: 264, 270, 563, 633, 648.
 me = mu (nom): 266, 536, 636.
 (*)me-e = me: 536, 633.
 (*)me-en = men: 536, 597.
 tu-mu₂me-er = tumu₂mir: 264, 553, 597, 634.
 me-li-im = me-lam₂: 265, 563, 636.
 me-li-ya = me-li-e-a: 548, 621.
 me-saḡ = ne-saḡ: 548, 642.
 me-ti-eš = me-teš₂: 568, 616.
 (m)i = e (dans mi = {m + e}): 231, 343:98, 567, 614, 647.
 mi = me: 233, 536, 548, 633.
 mi = me-e: 264, 270, 563, 633, 648.
 mi = me₃: 233, 326:29 sq., 548, 633.
 mi = mi₂: 536, 583.
 mi-n = ḡin: → ḡi₆-n.
 mi-e = me ({m + e}): 333 sq. l. 67 sq.
 mi-en = me-en: 255, 536, 548, 555, 563, 626, 633 sq.
 mi-i = me-e: 264, 270, 563, 633, 648.
 mi-im = mi₂: 573, 597, 626.
 (m)i-ir = ir-ir⁸⁴: 534, 542⁸⁵, 611, 612, 648.
 (*)mi-ir = (tumu₂)mir: 264, 553, 569, 597, 616, 634.
 mi-ir-mi-ir = mir-mir: 553, 597, 630.
 mi-ir-si = me-er-si: 267, 548, 631, 634.
 mi-li = me-lam₂: 251, 263, 265, 293, 536, 542, 597, 612, 636, 642.
 mi-li-im = me-lam₂: 263, 265, 536, 597, 636, 642.

⁸³ J'ai de la peine à croire que dans u₂ lul-la gu₇/a lul-la naḡ (X₄₀ = VS 10, 182 rev. 1 sq.), lul-la recouvre lu₃-lu₃, et non {lul + a}.

Mais il est vrai que lul(-la) ne détermine que très rarement nourriture ou boisson (cf. K. Lämmerhirt, AOAT 348 [2010] 275).

⁸⁴ Pour VAT 615+ o. i 11' = VS 31 i 11': mu-ud-na-ḡu₁₀ u₃-šu-gal-an¹²-na-ḡu₁₀ u₃-maš-še₃¹² ga-na-mi-ir, comp. Mirelman/Sallaberger, ZA 104, 181:17': mu-ud-na-ḡu₁₀ u₃-ušumgal-an-na-ra amaš-še₃ ga-an-na-ir-ir.

⁸⁵ A la p. 642 s.v. ga-na-mi-ir = ga-an-na-ir-ir (de même p. 611) et mi-ir = -an-ir-ir (de même p. 612)!

mi-na(-ši) = me-na(-še₃): 450, 563, 634.
 mi-ri = me-ri (pied): 266, 267, 536, 548, 563, 631 sq., 634.
 tu-ni^{mi}mi-ri = tumu^{mir}mir⁸⁶: 264, 563, 569, 606, 616, 634.
 mi-te-iš(-e) = me-teš₂: 255, 536, 597, 626, 634.
 mu = dumu: 545, 551, 613.
 mu = mu 551, 613.
 mu = mu₂: 275, 324:23, 536, 548, 584.
 mu-d = mud: → ^dnu-dim2-mu-d.
 mu-g = mug: 560, 606.
 (m)u-g = ug₅ (dans dam(-)mu-ga-na): 251, 540, 541, 660, 611.
 (m)u-s = us₂: 568, 616.
 mu-š = muš₃⁸⁷: 536, 597.
 mu-di-n = mu-tin: 536, 610.
 mu-ga-r = mu-un-gar₃: 233, 259, 352:116, 548, 597, 623.
 mu-gi = mu-gi₁₇-ib: 344:99.
 mu-gi-b = mu-gi₁₇-ib: 270, 548, 597, 642.
 mu-gi-ib = mu-gi₁₇-ib/mu-gig: 270, 271, 536, 548, 556, 563, 583 sq., 642.
 mu-gi-ib₂ = mu-gi₁₇-ib/mu-gig: 48, 416, 536, 563, 583 sq.
 mu-gi₄-ib = mu-gi₁₇-ib/mu-gig: 553, 584.
 mu-le-el = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 251, 450, 563, 569, 610, 620, 634.
 mu-li = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 553, 555, 623.
 mu-li-l = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 251, 563, 568, 569, 610, 615, 620, 634.
 (^d)mu-lil₂ = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 233, 251, 270, 323:21, 548, 551, 610, 619.
 mu-lu-l(u) = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 251, 267, 563, 610, 631, 634.
 *mu-lu-ug = bulug⁸⁸: 256, 262, 558, 590, 636.
 mu-mu = mu₁₁-mu₁₁: 573, 584, 630.
 mu-ni₅-in-ma-ar = ^{ġis}nim-mar⁸⁹: 564, 598, 623, 644, 646.
 mu-nu = mu-nu₂: 563, 584.
 *mu-nu-us₂ = munus: 276.
 mu-ru(-š) = ġurus⁹⁰: 232, 327:35, 547, 594, 624.
 (*)mu-ru-um-ša = mur-ša₄: 563, 597, 631.
 mu-ru-um-šu-a = mur-ša₄: 563, 597, 631.
 mu-sa-ra = mu-sar-ra: 576, 597.
 mu-su-ur = ġiš-ur₃⁹¹: 533, 542, 594, 612, 643.
 *mu-še-eġ₃ = mušen: 258, 264, 536, 597, 634.
 *mu-še-en = mušen: 258, 264, 536, 597, 634.
 mu-še₃ = mušen: 258, 264, 563, 624, 634.
 mu-ši-in = mušen: 264, 536, 551, 553, 597, 613, 634.
 mu-ti-n = mu-tin: 536, 563, 597, 610.
 mu-ti-na = mu-tin-an-na: 568, 616.
 mu-ti-in = mu-tin: 553, 563, 597.
 mu-ti-na-na = mu-tin-an-na: 536, 542, 543, 548, 610, 612, 619.
 *mu-u₂ = mu₂: 275.
 (*)mu-ud = mud: 563, 573, 597.
 mu-ud-nu = mu-ud-na: 266, 563, 631.
 (*)mu-ul = mul: 553, 563, 573, 597.
 mu-ul-la = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 536, 625.
^dmu-ul-li = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 536, 625.
^dmu-ul-li-l = ^dmu-ul-lil₂: 536, 625.
 mu-ul-mu-ul = mul-mul: 563, 597, 630.
 mu-un = u₃-mu-un: 268, 271, 550, 602.
 mu-ur-ša₄ = mur/ur₅-ša₄⁹²: 578, 597.
 mu-ur-gu = murgu₂: 563, 573, 597.
 mu-uš = muš: 573, 597.

⁸⁶ Delnero ^{im}mir (264, 563, 634) ou ^{tumu}mi-ir-re (569, 616).

⁸⁷ Dans e-mu-š = e₂-muš₃.

⁸⁸ Vue l'alternance bien connue entre /m/ et /b/, il me semble abusif de corriger MU en "bu!" comme le fait Delnero.

⁸⁹ Plus exactement mu-ni₅-in-ma-ar est une graphie non-standard de mu-nim-mar, ES pour /ġešnimbar/.

⁹⁰ mu-ru(-š) recouvre en fait /muruš/, ES pour ġurus.

⁹¹ Ainsi Delnero; préférable serait ġu₁₀-su-ur = (^{ġes})ġušur.

⁹² Delnero oscille entre ur₅(-ša₄) (579) et "mur₅(-ša₄)" (p. 597; correct serait mur-ša₄).

mu-uš = muš₃: 536, 548, 597.
 mu₂-ti-in = mu-tin: 553, 597.
 mu₂-ti-na-na = mu-tin-an-na: 554, 614.
 munus-s = munus: 554, 614.
 *mur-gu₄ = murgu₂: 563, 597.
 na = a-na: 551.
 (n)a = a₂: → e₂-na-na.
 (n)a = AK: 551, 613.
 (n)a = an (ciel): 550, 613, 614; → ga-ša-na.
 na = na-aĝ₂: 258, 323:20, 548, 563, 624.
 na = nun: → e₂-na-na.
 ṛna[˘]-ĝ = na-aĝ₂: 279:3, 568, 616.
 (*)na-ĝ: V. (*)na-ĝ(a₂)
 (n)a-k = AK: 568, 616.
 na-m = nam: 575, 618.
 (n)a-n = an (ciel): 556 et 614⁹³; → ga-ša-na-na, ka-ša-aĝ₂-na-na, ka-ša-an-na-na, ka-ša-na-na, mu-ti-na-na, NIN-na-na.
 (*)na-aĝ = naĝ: 536, 548, 598.
 *na-aĝ₂-ĝa₂ = naĝ: 536, 598.
 na-aĝ₂-lu-lu = na-aĝ₂-lu₂-ulu₃⁹⁴: 563, 648.
 na-am = na-aĝ₂: 563, 624, 644.
 na-am = nam: 573, 598.
 na-am-ĥa = nam-ĥe₂: 575, 617.
 na-am-ni-r = nam-nir: → nu-na-am-ni-r.
 na-am-nu-un = nam-nun: 573.
 na-am-ta-r = na-aĝ₂-tar: 563, 598, 623, 644.
 (n)a-an = an (ciel): → ga-ša-na-an.
 na-di-g = na-de₅-g: 573, 584.
 na-gi = na-aĝ₂-gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: 568, 616.
 na-gi-le-em = na-aĝ₂-gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: 568, 616.
 na-gu₄-u₈ = nam-gu₂: 577, 618.
 (*)na-ĝ(a₂) = naĝ: 536, 548, 563, 598, 606.
 na-ĝa₂-r = naĝar: 573, 575, 598, 617.
 na-lu-ga-l = nam-lugal: 529, 577, 589, 618, 640.
 na-na = na-nam: 233, 234, 548, 551, 613, 624.
 ᵀna-na = ᵀnamma: → ur-ᵀna-na(-ma).
 na-na-a = na-nam: 233, 344:100, 548, 624.
 ᵀna-na-ma = ᵀnamma: → ur-ᵀna-na(-ma).
 na-na-ya = ᵀnanna: 548, 551, 619, 621.
 (n)a-ra-[li] = a-ra-li: 569, 617.
 na-ta-r = nam/na-aĝ₂-tar: 542, 563, 598, 612, 623, 644.
 nam = nam₂: 537, 584.
 nam-da-g = nam-tag: 256, 537, 628, 642.
 nam-ĥi-i-a = nam-ĥe₂-a: 576, 634.
 nam-lu₂-lu₂ = nam-lu₂-ulu₃: 536, 625.
 nam-nu-n = nam₍₂₎-nun: 282, 542, 573, 610, 612.
 nam-ta-r = nam/na-aĝ₂-tar: 282, 563, 568, 574, 598, 607, 610, 616, 623, 644.
 nam-ta-ar = nam/na-aĝ₂-tar: 563, 598, 623, 644.
 ne = ni₂: 26, 264.
 ne-du-g = niĝ₂-du₁₀-g: 537, 623.
 ne-eĝ₃ = e-ne-eĝ₃: 569, 617.
 *ne-en = nin: 537, 623.
 ne-en = nin₉: 564, 598.
 ne-er = nir: 537, 598, 634.
 ne(-)ĝa₂-ra = niĝ₂(-)ĝar-ra⁹⁵: 266, 537, 542, 598, 612, 631.
 ne-ĝu₁₀-li-mu⁹⁶ = niĝ₂-ur₂-limmu₂: 537, 542, 598, 612.

⁹³ Dans nu-gi(-)na[˘]-na = (?) nu-gig-an-na; le /n/ initial est inexplicable.

⁹⁴ Delnero = na-aĝ₂-ulu₃.

⁹⁵ Attesté dans AO 3925 rev. 8' = Sulpae A 52 texte C. Le sens n'est pas très clair, mais ne(-)ĝa₂-ra recouvre plus probabl. niĝ₂ ĝar-ra (ainsi avec hésitation Delnero pp. 542 et 612) que niĝ₂-gur₁₁-ra (Delnero 266, etc.; gur₁₀ est une coquille pour gur₁₁).

⁹⁶ Delnero ne-mu-li-mu.

"ne-la₂-am" = me-lam₂⁹⁷: 263, 265, 536, 597, 636, 642.
 ne-mu-li-mu: → ne-ġu₁₀-li-mu.
 ne-ne = ni₁₀-ni₁₀: V. ni₅-ni₅.
 ne-ti = ġešt_{in}: 533, 594, 624, 643.
 ne-ti-in = ġešt_{in}: 533, 594, 643.
 (n)e₂⁹⁸ = e₃: 541, 611.
 ne₂-eš-ki = ġiš-gi: 286, 533, 594, 627, 633, 638, 643.
 (n)i = e: 575, 617.
 ni = ni₂: 250, 264, 537, 548, 563, 577, 584, 634.
 (*)ni = niġ₂: 564, 598, 644.
 ni-ġ = e-ne-eġ₃: 268, 269, 559, 591, 632.
 (n)i-l = il₂: 551, 567, 613, 615.
 ni-n = nin₉: 564, 606.
 (n)i-r = ir₂: 567, 615.
 ni-r = nir: → nu-na-am-ni-r.
 *ni-ge-en = niġin: 564, 598, 644.
 ni-ġa₂-r = niġin₃-ġar⁹⁹: 532, 598.
 ni-ġa₂-ar = niġin₃-ġar: 532, 598.
 ni-ġar = niġin₃-ġar: 532, 598.
 *ni-ġe₆-eġ₃ = niġin: 564, 598, 644.
 *ni-ġe₆-en = niġin: 564, 598, 644.
 "ni-ġi₆-in = niġin"¹⁰⁰: 564, 598, 644.
 ni-ib-ru = nibru^{ki}: 250, 548, 551, 564, 598, 613.
 ni-ig = niġ₂: 271, 564, 598, 644.
 *ni-iġ₃ = niġ₂: 564, 598, 644.
 ni-iġ₃-ġar = niġin₃-mar: 560, 598, 646.
 ni-im-di-im-ma = niġ₂-dim₂-ma: 576, 598, 644.
 ni-im-ġu-lu-di-ma = niġ₂-ġul-dim₂-ma: 644, 576, 598, 644.
 *ni-in = nin: 537, 623.
 (*)ni-in = nin₉: 564, 598.
 ni-in-gi-li = ^dnin-kilim: 283, 286, 573, 598.
 (n)i-in-ki = ^den-ki¹⁰¹: 283, 575, 617.
 (n)i-in-ki-id = ^den-ki¹⁰²: 575, 617.
 ni-in-ni-im-ma = ^dnin-imma₃: 564, 598.
 ni-in-si = nisi: 573.
 ni-in-ta = nita: 576, 598.
 ni-iš = ġiš₃: 286, 572, 643.
 ni-iš-gi = ġiš-gi: 286, 572, 643.
 ni-iš-ġu-ur = ġiš-ġur: 572, 643.
 ni-iš-tu = ġeštug₂: 533, 594, 643.
 (n)i-lu = i-lu: 568, 615.
 ni-ma-r = niġin₃-mar: 564, 598, 646.
 ni-mi-ir = nimgir¹⁰³: 564, 598, 623.
 ni-mi-mar = ^{ġi₅}nim-mar: 548, 551, 598, 619.
 NI-na-na = ^dinana: 547, 551, 595, 619, 622.
 ni-ni = ni₁₀-ni₁₀: 264, 537, 564, 584, 630, 634.
 ni-su-ub = niġ₂-su-ub: 537, 623.
 ni-zi-ġa₂-al = niġ₂-zi-ġal₂: 542, 612.
 ni₅¹⁰⁴ = ni₂: 563, 584, 634.
 ni₅ = nin: 537, 542, 612, 623.

⁹⁷ Lire avec Sjöberg (JCS 34, 74 n° 5:15' et 17') [x](-)x'(-)ne me^{l2}-am(-)mu-(...) // [xxx]-e me-a mu-(...).

⁹⁸ Delnero ni.

⁹⁹ niġin₃-gar (ainsi Delnero) est certainement un lapsus; mieux serait de toute façon niġar^{ġar} (v. Attinger, GSF 801 et n. 2391 avec litt. ant.).

¹⁰⁰ Dans X₄₆ (= PBS 10/2, 13) rev. 7, ni-ġi₆-in est une graphie de niġen₆ (v. en dernier lieu A. Löhnert, AOAT 365 [2009] 439 sq./443:6').

¹⁰¹ Mais voir ma critique dans GSF 347 n. 854.

¹⁰² V. la note précédente.

¹⁰³ Mieux ni-ġi₆-ir = niġir.

¹⁰⁴ Dans la plupart des cas, il serait préférable de lire ne plutôt que ni₅; comp. l'auteur lui-même pour ne-du-g = niġ₂-du₁₀-g (pp. 537 et 623), ne-ġa₂-ra = niġ₂-gur₁₁ (266, etc.; mais v. la note ad loc.) et ne-mu-li-mu = niġ₂-ur₂-limmu₂ (p. 537, etc.). Pour NE.NE = ni₁₀-ni₁₀, il translittère ne-ne à la p. 264, mais sinon ni₅-ni₅ (p. 564, etc.).

ni₅-ba = niĝ₂-ba: 564, 623.
 ni₅-in-ba = nidba: 537, 598.
 ni₅-in-du-g = niĝ₂-du₁₀-g: 537, 598.
 ni₅-iš-gi = ĝiš-gi: 286, 561, 633, 638, 643.
 ni₅-ni₅ = ni₁₀-ni₁₀: 264, 564, 584, 630, 634.
 ni₅-pa-ar = ĝi₆-par₃: 561, 643.
 ni₅-ta-na = nitadam: 537, 598.
 niG₂-g = niĝ₂: 568, 616.
 niĝ₂-gi-li = ^dnin-kilim: 573, 598.
 niĝ₂-gi-li-li = ^dnin-kilim: 283, 286, 573, 598.
 niĝ₂-a₂-r = niĝin₃-mar: 560, 598, 646.
 niĝ₂-ĝa₂-ka = niĝ₂-AK-a: 575, 618.
 niĝ₂-ĥu-lu-di-ma = niĝ₂-ĥulu-dim₂-ma: 573, 576, 598, 644.
 niĝ₂-ĥu-ur-su-ga = ^dnin-ĥur-saĝ: 553, 555, 598, 620, 631.
 NIN-an-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 332:63.
 nin-e-gal-la = ^dnin-e₂-gal-la: 564, 584.
 NIN-na-na = ga-ša-an-an-na: 268, 332:63, 553, 647.
 nu = nu₂: 537, 548, 551, 553, 564, 568, 584, 613, 616, 648; ĝiš-nu, mu-nu.
 nu = nun: 575, 617; → a₂-nu-ĝal₂, ĝa₂-nu-ma-aĥ.
 nu-n = nun: 537, 575, 610, 617; → a-nu-na, ma-nu-n, nam₍₂₎-nu-n.
^dnu-dim₂-mu-d = ^dnu-dim₂-mud: 548, 551, 598, 619.
 nu-ga-al = nun-gal: 284, 573, 623.
 nu-gi = mu-gi₁₇-ib/mu-gig: 102:4, 168, 233, 270, 317:2, 344:99, 548, 551, 556¹⁰⁵, 613, 614, 642, 646, 648.
 nu-gi₆-i-g¹⁰⁶ = nu-gig: 537, 598, 646.
 nu-ĝi(n) = nu-gig (dans nu-ĝin-na = (?) nu-gig an-na): 568, 616.
 nu-ya = nu-me-a: 548, 622.
 nu-mi-i-g = nu-gig: → nu-gi₆-i-g.
 nu-mu = numun: 284, 573, 623.
 nu-mu₂-un = ^{u2}numun₂: 252, 553, 555, 599, 620.
 nu-na-am-ni-r = ^dnu-nam-nir: 576, 599.
 nu-um = nu₂: 233, 255, 328:38, 365, 548, 584, 626.
 (*)nu-un = nun: 276, 537, 564, 599; → en-a-nu-un, na-am-nu-un.
 nu-uš-ki = nu-siki: 258, 537, 622, 646.
 pa = pa₅: 573, 584.
 pa-d = pa(d)₃: 270, 548, 564, 584, 607, 610, 640.
 pa-r = pa₅-r: 537, 564, 584.
 pa-t = bad: 544, 604, 628, 640.
 *pa-a = pad₃: 537, 607, 640.
 pa-an-su-ur₂ = ^{ĝi₈}bansur: 256, 262, 283, 529, 589, 628, 640.
 *pa-an-šu[?]-ur[?] = ^{ĝi₈}bansur: 256, 262, 558, 589, 640.
 pa-ap = pap: → a-pa-ap
 *pa-ar = par₄: 549, 599, 641.
 pa-bi-il-sa-aĝ₂ = ^dpa-bil₂-saĝ: 564, 599.
 pa-la = bala: → a-aš₂-pa-la.
 pa-pa-ar = babbar: 256, 262, 267, 270, 275, 285, 287, 544, 589, 625, 628, 640.
 pa-ra(-g) = bara₂(-g): 262, 529, 544, 550(?), 558, 576, 577, 589, 618, 628, 640.
 pa₃ = pa: → an-pa₃.
 pa₃-d/r = pad₃: 553, 607, 610.
 pa₃-an-su-r = ^{ĝi₈}bansur: 256, 262, 283, 529, 589, 628, 640.
 pa₃-e = pa-e₃: 537, 584.
 pa₃-e₃ = pa-e₃: 542, 612.
 (p)e = e: 576.
 pe-eš = peš₁₀¹⁰⁷: 255, 564, 568, 616, 626.
 pe-pe = peš-peš (vb.): 564, 630.
 pe-pe-eš = peš-peš (vb.): 564, 630.

¹⁰⁵ L'entrée nu-gi-na = mu-gig (aussi p. 642) est un peu trompeuse. Aux pp. 556 et 614, Delnero lit en revanche nu-gi-na-na = mu-gi₁₇-ib an-na. Dans Ha₁ o. 2 = TIM 9, 31:2, on a toutefois probabl. nu-ge[?] an[?]-na = nu-ge₁₇ an-na (de même S.M. Maul, CTMMA 2 [2005] 78).

¹⁰⁶ Delnero nu-mi-i-ga.

¹⁰⁷ Delnero peš.

pi-ri-iġ¹⁰⁸ = piriġ: 573, 599.
 (*)pu = pu¹⁰⁹: 537, 573, 584, 641.
 *pu-u₂ = pu₂: 537, 641.
 qa = ga (vb.): 232, 546, 621, 626, 637.
 qa = ga-am₃ (ES de ga₆-ġ): 328:40 sq.
 qa = gi (jeune femme): 232, 256, 326:33, 546, 627, 638.
 qa-na = gana¹¹⁰: 284, 286, 571, 593, 621, 627, 629, 637.
 (r)a = an: → du-ra-ki.
 (r)a-n = an (ciel) 283, 556, 575, 614, 617; → du-bu-ra-na, du-^rx^r-ar-ra-na.
 re = (e-)re₇: 559, 580, 604.
 *re-e = (e-)re₇: 559, 580.
 ri-b = rib: 537, 607, 610.
 ri-g = rig₇: 554, 607, 610.
 ri-n = ġ^{is}erin: 258, 560, 622.
 *ri-ib = rib: 537, 607.
 ru = uru₂: 233, 343:98, 550, 613.
 ru-ba-r = uru₂-bar: 251, 551, 613.
 (r)u-^dutu = ^dutu: 568, 616.
 sa = sa₂: 537, 549, 556, 585.
 sa = sa₆: 573, 584.
 sa = sa₁₀: 573, 585.
 *sa = saġ: 263, 537, 599.
 sa-g = sa₆-g: 558 (dans da-mu-sa-ga), 564, 579 (dans da-mu-sa-ga), 585.
 sa-g = saġ: 577, 618.
 sa-ġ = saġ: 233, 251, 263, 282, 283, 326:30, 328:40, 346:104, 549, 564, 573, 575, 607, 610, 618, 644; → ħa-an-
 du-ur-sa-ġa₂, ħu-ur₂-sa₂-ġ, ħur-sa-ġ.
 sa-r = sar: 577, 607, 610; → du₁₀-sa-r, dub-sa-r, mu-sa-ra.
 *sa-ag = sig₃: 265, 549, 607.
 (*)sa-aġ₂ = saġ: 263, 537, 599; → pa-bi-il-sa-aġ₂.
 sa-an = saġ: 263, 564, 644.
 sa-ar = sar: → du-ub[?]-sa-ar.
 sa-ar-sa-r = sar-sar: 254, 564, 630.
 sa-bar = sa-par₃: 549, 599, 641.
 sa-gi = sagi: 549, 599.
 sa-gi-ki-ga = saġ-gegge-ga: 568, 616.
 sa-ħa = saħar: 564, 599, 624.
 sa-ħa-r = saħar: 564, 573, 599.
 (*)sa-ħa-ar = saħar: 275, 564, 577, 599.
 *sa-ki-ir = šakir₃: 266, 549, 600, 631, 645.
 sa-pa = sipa: 266, 564, 599, 631.
 sa-sa-r = sar-sar: 254, 564, 630.
 "sa₂ = saġ": Dans 242:22¹¹¹, lire an-dil₂(-e) lugal-la // an-de-el lu₂-ga-[...] // an-di(-)lu₂-ga-la //¹¹².
 sa₂-g = sig₃: 265, 564, 567, 607, 610, 615, 636.
 sa₂-ġ = saġ: → ħu-ur₂-sa₂-ġ.
 sa₂-ab-ra = sa-par₃: 564.
 sa₂-sa₂ = sa₆-sa₆: 537, 585.
 sa₂-sa₂-g = sig₃-sig₃: 265, 564, 567, 607, 610, 615, 630, 636.
 sa₅-ki = saġ-ki: 324:24.
 saġ-ki-gi-ki-ak = saġ-gegge-ga-ka¹¹³: 556, 614.
 *se-es = šeš: 565, 635, 645.
 *se₂-eš-kur = sizkur₂: 565, 599, 645.
 *se-eš₃ = šeš: 549, 607, 635¹¹⁴, 645.
 si = si₃: 564, 574, 585.
 si-g = si₃-g: 537, 585, 646.

¹⁰⁸ Sic, pas -iġ₂.

¹⁰⁹ Pour BU = pu₂, Delnero translittère BU bu dans les textes rituels (ne provenant pas de Tell Haddad), mais pu dans les incantations de Tell Haddad et les textes lexicaux. Les raisons à cette manière de faire m'échappent.

¹¹⁰ Sic, v. p. 286, etc.

¹¹¹ Cf. aussi pp. 542 et 612 s.v. sa₂-el-lu₂-ga(-al).

¹¹² Cf. Attinger, GSF 171 avec n. 297.

¹¹³ Delnero saġ-ġi₆-ga-ka; pour d'autres graphies non-standard, v. en dernier lieu Attinger, GSF 404.

¹¹⁴ Aux pp. 635 et 645, enregistré fautivement s.v. šir₃.

si-g = sig₃: 233, 265, 345:102, 549, 564, 607, 610, 636.
 si-m = šem₅: → er₂-si-ma.
 si-q = si₃-g: → ki-si-qa.
 si-r = šir₃: → si-r(a).
 si-s = šeš: 233, 352-353:118, 549, 565, 607, 635, 645.
 si-il = šul: 266, 556, 600, 636, 645.
 (*)si-ir = šir₃: 264, 414:24(?), 539, 565, 600, 635, 645.
 *si-ke-el = sikil: 564, 599.
 si-ki = siki: 538, 564, 574, 599; → nu-uš-ki.
 si-ki = sikil 564, ; → ki-si-ki.
 (*)si-ki-il = sikil: 564, 599.
 si-ki-ir = šakir₃: 612, 549, 600, 631, 644.
 (*)si-la = sila: 275, 538, 543, 574, 599, 612; → (a)š(-)si-la.
 (*)si-la = sila₄: 538, 599.
 si-li = silim: 578, 618.
 si-li-g = silig: 538, 599.
 *si-li-ig = silig: 538, 599.
 si-li-m = silim: 250, 538, 599.
 (*)si-li-im = silim: 250, 538, 599.
 si-li-ši-a = silim-eš₂-am₃: 578, 618.
 si-ma = su-lim-ma: 259, 538, 647.
 si-pa = sipa: 269, 538, 564, 577, 599.
 si-pa₃-d = sipa: 269, 538, 599.
 si-r(a) = šir₃: 264, 549, 607, 610, 635, 645.
 "si-si = i-si-iš"¹¹⁵: 534, 644, 646.
 si-si-d = sed₅-sed₅: 574.
 *si₂-iš-ku-ur = sizkur₂: 565, 599, 645.
 *si₂-iš-kur = sizkur₂: 565, 599, 645.
 sila₃ = sila₄: 554, 585.
 sila₄-amar = sila₃-ġar¹¹⁶: 564, 644, 648.
 su = su₃: 538, 565, 585.
 su = su₆: 271, 538, 585.
 su-r = sur: 538, 607, 610.
 su-a = sa₂: 564, 585.
 su-an = usan: 550, 612.
 su-ba = su₈-ba: 250, 538, 549, 555, 565, 585.
 su-bi = suba₍₂₎: 538, 600, 645.
 su-bi₂ = suba₍₂₎: 600, 645.
 su-bu-r = šubur: 560, 565, 600.
 su-da-aġ₂ = su₃-ra₂-aġ₂: 538, 646.
 su-en = ^dsuen: 538, 543, 549, 551, 600, 619, 645.
 (*)su-ḥu-uš = suḥuš: 538, 600.
 su-ku-d = sukud: 262, 538, 565, 600, 642.
 su-ku-t = sukud: 262, 565, 600, 642.
 su-la = sum₄-la₂: → su-um-la-su-la.
 su-lu-um = su₁₁-lum: 549, 599.
 su-mu-n = sumun₂: 532, 600, 627, 637.
 su-mu-un-ga-an = ^dsumuqan: 565, 600.
 su-pa₃-e = ^dšul-pa-e₃: 539, 542, 543, 612, 619, 623.
 su-qa-al = sukkal: 284, 574, 621, 627, 639.
 "su-ra-ga = sur₉-gal": → sur-ru-ga.
 su-su = šuš₂-šuš₂: 577, 618.
 su-te-en = su-din^{mušen}: 286, 574, 642.
 su-ud = su₃: 255, 538, 549, 585, 626.
 su-ud = ^dsud₃¹¹⁷: 565, 600.
 su-um-la-su-la = sum₄-la₂-sum₄-la₂¹¹⁸: 228:80, 229, 542 (lire su-um-, pas sum-), 612 (id.).

¹¹⁵ Dans BM 78193 o. 8' = CT 44, 13:8', si-si ma-ma (ES) est une graphie non-standard pour si₁₂-si₁₂ ma-ma; cf. Attinger, GSF 479 et n. 1286 avec litt. ant.

¹¹⁶ Préférable serait sila₄-mar₂ = *sila₃-mar, ES pour sila₃-ġar.

¹¹⁷ ^dsud (Delnero) est une coquille.

¹¹⁸ Delnero hésite entre sum₄-la₂-sum₄-la₂ (228 sq.) et su₆-la₂-su₆-la₂ (542 et 612)

su-ur-su-ur = sur-sur: 284, 574, 600, 630.
 su-ur₂ = sur: 538, 607.
 su-us₂-su = su₃-su₃: 574.
 *su₂-um = su₆: 538, 585.
 su₃-n = sun₂: 549, 607, 610.
 su₈-bi = suba: 565, 600.
 sur-ru-ga = sur₉-gal¹¹⁹: 565, 647.
 ša = AK¹²⁰: 528, 579.
 ša = ša₃: 233, 271, 345:101, 538, 549, 565, 574, 585; → a-ša, a-ša-g.
 ša = ša₄: 549, 555, 585; → en-ša, ir-ša-ni-ša, mu-ru-um-ša.
 ša-p = ša₃-b: 565, 585, 628, 641.
 ša-ar = šar₂: 574, 600.
 ša-ar-ša-r = šar₂-šar₂: 630, 574, 600, 630.
 ša-ĝa₂ = sanga₂¹²¹: 573, 644.
 *ša-ki-ir = šakir₃: 266, 549, 600, 631, 645.
 ša-ni-ša = ša₃-ne-ša₄: → ir-ša-ni-ša.
 ša-ša-r = šar₂-šar₂: 538, 543, 612, 630.
 ša₃ = a-ša₃: 231, 258, 544, 557, 622.
 ša₃-p = ša₃-b: 554, 585, 607, 628, 641.
 še-ĝ = šeĝ₃: 538, 607, 610.
 še-n = šen: 233, 282, 345-346:103, 549, 565, 574, 607, 610.
 še-en-di-li = šen-dili₂: 565, 600.
 še-še = še₂₂-še₂₂: 265, 347:105, 555, 565, 586, 630, 635; → i-še še-še, ir-ši še-še.
 še-še-en = šen-šen: 565, 600, 630.
 še₃ = še-er: 567, 568, 615, 616.
 še₃-er = šir₃: 264, 539, 600, 635.
 šeš-š = šeš (pas ses): 542, 612.
 ši = še ("grain"): 264, 538, 554, 556, 565, 585, 634.
 ši = šeĝ₃: 565, 624, 635.
 ši = šu ("main"): 266, 565, 636.
 ši-b = še-eb (dans ši(-)be₂-kur-ra = še-eb e₂-kur-ra): 265, 565, 569¹²², 607, 616, 634.
 (š)i-d = i₇: 568, 616.
 ši-m = šim: 538, 607.
 ši-bar = šeg₉-bar: 258, 538, 623, 647.
 ši-im = šim: 538, 600; → u₃-ši-im.
 ši-in-ka = še-en-ka₆¹²³: 565, 585, 634.
 [ši]-iš-ku-r¹²⁴ = sizkur₂: 565, 599, 645.
 (š)i-re = (e-)re₇: 559, 580, 604.
 ši-še = še₂₂-še₂₂: 265, 565, 586, 630, 635.
 ši-ši = še₂₂-še₂₂: 239:14', 265, 347:105, 538, 630, 635.
 šim-bi₂ = šim-bi: 554, 586.
 šu = šu₂: 554, 586.
 šu = šub: 238:5' sq., 258, 338 sq. ll. 83-85, 539, 554, 624.
 šu = šum₂: 577, 624.
 šu-b = šub: 539, 607, 610.
 šu-a = ša₄: → mu-ru-um-šu-a.
 (*)šu-du = šud₃: 539, 600.
 šu-du₆ = šud₃: 549, 600.
 šu-ga-l = ušumgal: → ama-šu-ga-la-na.
 šu-gal = ušumgal → ama-šu-gal-a-na, ama-šu-gal-la-na.
 šu-ma-ar-gi = šu-mar-gi₄: 549, 600.
 šu-mi-n(i) = šumunda¹²⁵: 267, 565, 600, 631.
 šu-mu = /šumun/ (ES de ^{u2}numun₂)¹²⁶: 548, 551, 619, 624.
 šu-mu-gal = ušumgal (dans ama-R-la-na): 267, 268, 557, 567, 588, 615, 646.

¹¹⁹ su-ra-ga est une coquille pour sur-ru-ga, sur₈ pour sur₉.

¹²⁰ Mais cf. Attinger, GSF 971 avec n. 3042.

¹²¹ Sic. pas sanga (ainsi Delnero).

¹²² Aux pp. 569 et 616, lire še-eb (pas še-en).

¹²³ še-en-ka₅ est une coquille.

¹²⁴ La restitution [ši]- me semble arbitraire; sur les gloses et les graphies non-standard, v. aussi Attinger, GSF 927 avec n. 2874.

¹²⁵ Ainsi Delnero 266, etc., mais j'ai mes doutes; ^{u2}/šumun/ (ES de ^{u2}numun₂) entre sérieusement en considération.

¹²⁶ Delnero šu-mu = ^{u2}NUNUN₂.

šu-mu₂-un = ^{u2}šumunda¹²⁷: 554, 555, 600, 620, 624.
 šu-^rru[?]-m = šurum: 549, 600.
 šu-šu = šu₂-šu₂: 539, 586.
 šu-šu-ub = šub-šub: 556, 600, 630.
 šu-ub = šub: 539, 565, 574, 600.
 šu-ud-da = šud₃: 549, 600.
 šu-um-du = šu-um-du-um: 565, 607.
 šu₂ = šum₂: 539, 624.
 ta-b = dab₅: 262, 530, 604, 608, 640.
 ta-ḥ = daḥ: 571, 641.
 ta-p = tab: 282, 285, 574, 607, 610, 628, 641.
 ta-r = tar: 233, 282, 323:20, 539, 542, 549, 554, 565, 574, 575, 607, 610, 618; → na-am-ta-r, na-ta-r, nam-ta-r(a).
 ta-ab = tab: 285, 574, 600, 641.
 ta-ak = tak₄: 574, 600.
 ta-al-[...] = dalla: 530, 590, 641.
 ta-ar = tar: → ka-ta-ar.
 ta-ta = tag-tag: 574, 630.
 te-l = til₃: 262, 269, 539, 607, 642.
 *te-e = te: 549, 626, 635¹²⁸.
 te-e-r = tir¹²⁹: 572, 594, 635, 643.
 (*)te-er = tir: 264, 539, 601, 630, 635.
 (*)te-eš = teš₂: 565, 626, 635; → ga-te-eš.
 te-te-er = tir-tir: 264, 539, 630, 635.
 ti = di: → maḥ-ti.
 ti = te: 549, 565, 635.
 ti-r = tir: 264, 539, 607, 610, 635.
 ti-bi-r = tibir: 574, 601.
 *ti-e = te: 549, 626, 635¹³⁰.
 ti-el = til₃: 574, 601, 626.
 (*)ti-eš = teš₂: 565, 626, 635; → me-ti-eš.
 ti-gi = tigi: 539, 601.
 ti-il = til₃: 250 sq., 262, 539, 549, 554, 555, 565, 574, 601, 642.
 ti-il = tin: 560 (dans ga-ša-an-ti-il-lu-ba), 601 (id.).
 ti-il-lu-ba = tin-ug₅-ba: → ga-ša-an-ti-il-lu-ba.
 ti-in = tin: 539, 601; → mu-ti-in, ne-ti-in.
 til = til₃: 262, 345-346:103, 539, 586, 642.
 tu = du₃: → ma-tu.
 tu = du₁₁: 283, 575, 617, 641.
 tu = ti (dans šu ti): 267, 539, 542, 612, 631.
 tu = tu₅: 539, 586.
 tu = tu₆: 574, 586.
 (*)tu = tug₂/tu₉¹³¹: 256, 262, 351:115, 642.
 tu = tuš: 539, 608.
 tu-b = tu₁₁-b: 336:75.
 tu-b = dub: 559, 604, 641.
 tu-b = dub₂: 530, 545, 552, 559, 576, 591, 604, 608, 640, 641.
 tu-g = du₁₁-g; 270, 545, 580.
 tu-p = dub₂: 168, 232, 318:6, 333:65, 545, 604, 608, 628, 640, 641.
 tu-m = tum₂: 566, 607, 610.
 tu-r = tur: 539, 608, 610.
 tu-r = tur₃: 539, 608, 610.
 tu-s = tuš: 539, 608.
 tu-š = tuš: 334:70, 539, 554, 566, 568, 601, 608, 615; → ki-tu-š.
 (*)tu-ku = tuku: 233, 327 sq.:36 (<tu->ku) sq.), 539, 543, 549, 566, 601, 612.
 *tu-ku-ul = tukul: 275.

¹²⁷ Ainsi Delnero, mais plus probabl. = šu-mu-(u)n, ES de ^{u2}numun₂.

¹²⁸ Enregistré à tort s.v. teš₂.

¹²⁹ V. la note à propos de ḡi-iš = ḡiš.

¹³⁰ Enregistré à tort s.v. teš₂.

¹³¹ Delnero oscille entre tug₂ (le plus souvent) et tu₉ (par ex. 256). Aux pp. 233, 549 et 586, il parle même d'une graphie non-standard tu₉ = tug₂, mais j'ignore ce qu'il entend par là (la référence ne m'est pas claire).

tu-mi = *tumu-e: 263, 566, 569, 601, 616, 642.
 tu-mu = dumu: 262, 531, 559, 591, 641.
 tu-mu = tumu: 539, 554, 574, 601.
 tu-ni = tumu (dét.): 263, 264, 563, 566, 569, 601, 606, 616, 634, 642.
 tu-ni-nu-ra = tu₆ en₂-e₂-nu-ru: 571, 592.
 tu-tu = tur-tur: 233, 255, 284, , 341:93, 549, 630.
 tu-tu-b = dub₂-dub₂: 559, 604, 629, 640, 641.
 tu-tu-r = tur-tur: 228, 255, 284, 539, 608, 630.
 tu-tu-ub = dub₂-dub₂: 559, 604, 629, 640, 641.
 tu-tu-ur = tur-tur: 228, 255, 284, 539, 574, 601, 630.
 *tu-u₂ = tug₂/tu₉: 256, 262, 549, 586, 642.
 *tu-u₂ = tumu: 263, 539, 601.
 *tu-u₄ = tug₂/tu₉: 256, 262, 549, 586, 642.
 (*)tu-ub = dub₂: 530, 545, 559, 591, 604, 629, 640, 641.
 tu-um = tum₂: 566, 601, 607.
 tu-ur = tur: 566, 574, 601.
 tu-ur = tur₃: 539, 566, 601.
 *tu-ur-tu-ur = tur-tur: 539, 608, 630.
 tu-ur₂ = tur₃: 539, 601.
 (*)tu-uš = tuš: 539, 549, 554, 601, 608; → ki-tu-uš, ku-tu-uš.
 tu-ut-ku = tuku-tuku: 539, 601.
 tur = tur₃: 554, 586.
 u-gu₃ = u₂-gu: 566, 586.
 u₂ = u₃ ("sommeil"): 566, 586.
 u₂ = u₄: 566, 586.
 u₂ = u₅: 550, 587.
 u₂ = u₈: 554, 587.
 u₂ = u_d₅: 233, 550, 624, 648.
 u₂ = ug₅: 540, 624.
 u₂-d = u₄-d: 569, 616.
 u₂-r = ur₂: 540 566, 608, 610; → a-u₂-r.
 u₂-r = ur₃: 275.
 u₂-du = udug¹³²: 283, 575, 618.
 u₂-du-ug = udug: 574, 602.
 u₂-ga = uga^{mušen}: 566, 602.
 u₂-li-li-la = u₃-li-li-la: 540, 586.
 u₂-mu¹³³ = u₃-mu-un: 268, 550, 551, 602, 614.
 u₂-nu = unu₂: 540, 550, 602.
 u₂-ri = urim: 577, 618.
 u₂-ri-m = urim^{ki134}: 577, 602.
 u₂-ri-in = urin: 566, 574, 602.
 "u₂-ru = ur¹³⁵: 556, 602.
 u₂-ru = uru₂: 332:62, 335:73, 554, 555, 566, 577, 602, 636.
 *u₂-ru-ga-al = /urugal/¹³⁶: 562, 595, 636.
 u₂-ši-im = u₂-šim: 566 et 601 X₄₆ r. 12¹³⁷.
 u₂-šu-ga-l = ušumgal: → a-ma-u₂-šu-ga-la-na.
 u₂-šu-um-gal = ušumgal: 282, 574, 603.
 *u₂-šu-ur = ušur: 566, 603.
 *u₂-šu-ur₂ = ušur: 566, 603.
 u₂-tu-ug = utug₂: 577, 603.
 u₂-u(d) = gu₄ (dans u₂-ud-li = gu₄ dili): 569, 616.
 u₂-ur = ur: 569, 617.
 u₃ = u₂: 250, 540, 543, 566, 586, 612.
 u₃ = u₄: 566, 586.

¹³² Sic, pas udug₂.

¹³³ Delnero u₂-mu-eĝ₃, mais le AĜ₂ qui suit est probabl. toujours la forme ES pour niĝ₂ (cf. p. 551 et 614).

¹³⁴ urim^{ki} (Delnero) est une coquille.

¹³⁵ Dans Ha₁ o. 7 = TIM 9, 31:7, lire probabl. ka-ša-an me u₂-ru-re (=?) /gašan/ me ur₄-ur₄-(r)e (pour me ur₄-ur₄-(r)e plutôt que me ur₄-ur₄, comp. Išme-Dagan K 3). Remarquer toutefois que d'après S.M. Maul (CTMMA 2 [2005] 79:9b' et comm. p. 82) le sens de me u₂(-)-ru(-)re serait obscur.

¹³⁶ Rangé par Delnero s.v. iri₁₁-gal.

¹³⁷ u₃-ši-im (Delnero) est une coquille.

u₃ = u₅: 540, 566, 587.
 u₃ = u_d₅: 569, 617.
 u₃ = u_g₃: 228, 229, 259.
 u₃ = u₃-mu-un: 268, 569, 617.
 u₃ = uru₂: 551, 613.
 u₃-d = u₄-d: 345:101, 540, 586, 587.
 u₃-g = ug₅: 282, 540, 541, 574, 608, 610, 611.
 u₃-r = ur₂: 275, 540, 608, 610; → a-u₃-r.
 u₃-bu-ur₂ = ubur: 540, 602.
 (*)u₃-bur = ubur: 540, 550, 602.
 u₃-du = u₃-tu: 540, 566, 602, 628, 642.
 u₃-ga = uga^{mušen}: 566, 602.
 u₃-ga = ugu: 574, 602.
 u₃-gal = ušumgal: 259, 282, 540, 542, 603, 612, 647.
 u₃-gu = ugu: 566, 602.
 u₃-gu₂ = u₂-gu: 566, 586.
 u₃-maš = amaš (après /u/): 267, 542, 528, 588, 612, 644.
 u₃-mu-n = u₃-mu-un: 268, 271, 540, 543, 550, 551, 556, 569, 601 sq., 612, 613, 614, 617.
 u₃-nu = unu₂: 540, 566, 602.
 u₃-nu-k = unug^{ki}: 566, 602, 621.
 u₃-nu-q = unug^{ki}: 254, 556, 602, 621, 627, 639.
 u₃-nu la = unu₂ la₂: 241 sq. l. 20'.
 u₃-nu [...] = unug^{ki}: 540, 602.
 u₃-ra = uru₂: 566, 602.
 u₃-ri-m = urim^{ki138}: 540, 543, 577, 602, 619.
 u₃-ru = uru₂: 540, 602.
 u₃-ši-im = u₂-šim: 566 et 601 X₁₀ r. 6¹³⁹.
 u₃-šu-r = ušur: 566, 603.
 u₃-šu-gal = ušumgal: 612, 624; → ama-u₃-šu-gal-a-na, u₃-šu-gal-la-na.
 u₃-šu-gal-a-na = (ama)-ušumgal-an-na: 267, 269, 540, 543, 557, 588, 603, 619, 624, 646.
 u₃-šu-um-gal = ušumgal → ama-u₃-šu-um-gal-an-na.
 *u₃-šu-ur = ušur: 566, 603.
 u₃-šu-ur₂ = ušur: 566, 603.
 u₃-[tu] = ^dutu: 566, 603.
 u₃-ur = ur₂: → a-u₃-ur.
 *u₄ = u: 274.
 u₄ = u₂: 233, 250, 549, 586.
 u₄ = ur: 3401:91.
 u₄-r = ur₂: → a-u₄-r.
 u₄-ga = uga^{mušen}: 233, 234, 328:39, 550, 552, 602, 620.
 u₄-lu = u₄ ħul: 234, 329:48, 551, 614.
 u₄-mu-n = u₃-mu-un: 268, 550, 602.
 u₄-ri-m = urim^{ki140}: 577, 602.
 *u₄-ru = uru₂: 540, 603.
 u₄-šu-a-qa = ur-šu-AK-a: 233, 254, 550, 551, 602, 614, 621, 624, 627, 635, 639.
 *u₄-šu-ur = ušur: 566, 603.
 u₄-tu = ^dutu: 554, 555, 603, 620.
 ub = ub₇: 540, 587.
 (u)d-li = dili (dans u₂-ud-li = gu₄ dili): 569, 616.
 ug-nu-um = ugnim¹⁴¹: 267, 336:75, 554, 602, 631.
 (u)ħ-la = ħul-a: 575, 618.
 (u)ħ-le = ħul (devant /e/): 575, 618.
 (u)ħ-lu = ħul: 283, 575, 618.
 (u)l-le = la₂ (devant /e/): 575, 617.
 u(m) = u₈: 569, 617.
 um-bi = umbin: 574, 624.
 um-ke-n = unken: 257, 540, 602, 629, 642.

¹³⁸ urim^{ki} (Delnero) est une coquille.

¹³⁹ Dans X₄₆ r. 12, lire u₂-ši-im.

¹⁴⁰ urim^{ki} (Delnero) est une coquille.

¹⁴¹ Mais cf. mes réticences dans GSF 1103 n. 3516.

(u)m-lu = mu-lu (dans el-lu-um-lu = e-lum mu-lu): 567, 615.
 um-MI-n = unken: 257, 540, 602, 629, 642.
 (u)m-mu-š = muš: 569, 617.
 *un-ke-en = unken: 257, 540, 602, 642.
 (*)ur = ur₂: 275, 281, 540, 574, 587; → a-ur.
 ur = ur₃: → ki-ur.
 ur-^dna-na(-ma) = ur-^dnamma¹⁴²: 577, 602.
 ur₂-ba-ra = ur-bar-ra: 540, 602.
 ur₂-bar¹⁴³ = ušbar: 566, 648.
 ur₂-ma-ḥ = ur-maḥ: 540, 608.
 ur₂-saḡ = ḥur-saḡ: 534, 542, 595, 611.
 ur₂-saḡ = ur-saḡ: 540, 587.
 *uru-gal = /urugal/¹⁴⁴: 562, 595, 636.
 uru₂^{ru} = uru₂: 234, 552, 649.
 uru₂-zi-ib₂^{ki} = uru₂-ze₂-eb^{ki}: 566, 603, 635.
 (u)s₂-ḥa-r = saḥar₂: → us₂-ḥa-ra.
 us₂-ḥa-ra = ^du₄-saḥar₂-ra: 258, 550, 552, 620, 622.
 uš = eš₃: 266, 546, 636.
 *uš = uš₂: 274.
 uš = uš₁₁: 574, 587.
 (u)š-ki = siki: → nu-uš-ki.
 ušum-gal = ušumgal: 282, 540, 603.
 ya = a-a: 254, 544, 621.
 ya = e₂¹⁴⁵: 232, 234, 254, 344:100, 546, 551, 613, 621.
 ya = me-a: → nu-ya.
 (y)a-n = an (ciel): → e₂-ya-na.
 ya-ḡu₁₀-ya-ḡu₁₀ = u₂-a-e-u₂-a: 566, 622.
 za = za₃: 281, 554, 566, 574, 587, 614.
 za-g = za₃: 541, 587.
 za-l = zal: 541, 566, 608, 610.
 (*)za-al = zal: 541, 554, 566, 603, 608, 630; → gi-ir-za-al.
 za-al-za-al = zal-zal: 255, 554, 603, 630.
 za-am-me-en = za₃-mi₂: 575, 618.
 *za-ar = zal: 541, 603.
 za-a(Š) = za-e (dans za-aŠ(-)si-la = za-e sila): 543, 612, 648.
 za-ba-r = zabar: 574, 603.
 za-ba-la = zabalām^{ki}: 252, 541, 543, 550, 552, 556, 566, 603, 643, 619, 620.
 za-gi = za-gin₃: 258, 277, 541, 556, 566, 603, 624.
 za-gi-n = za-gin₃: 541, 566, 603.
 (*)za-gi-in = za-gin₃: 258, 276 sq., 541, 603.
 za-la-k = zalag: 566, 603, 627, 639.
 (*)za-la-ag = zalag: 541, 603, 627, 639.
 ze₂ = za-e: 554, 614.
 ze₂ = ze₂-eḡ₃: 554, 603, 644.
 zi = izi: 232, 258, 323:19, 534¹⁴⁶, 547, 622, 646¹⁴⁷; → gi-zi-la.
 zi = za-e: 540, 648.
 zi = ze₂-eb: 566, 624, 636.
 zi-l = zil₂: 566, 603.
 zi-q = zi-g: 254, 550, 621, 627, 639.
 zi-ib₂ = ze₂-eb: → uru₂-zi-ib₂^{ki}.
 zi-il = zil₂: 566, 603.
 zi-ir-zi-ir = ze₂-er-ze₂-er: 541, 630.
 zi-zi-k = si₃-si₃-g/k: 537, 645, 646.
 zu = zu₂: 574, 587.

¹⁴² ^dur-namma est une coquille.

¹⁴³ Une lecture ušbar^{-bar}/ušbar^x^{bar} (Alster, ASJ 14, 15:156 A et Attinger, GSF 1136) est préférable.

¹⁴⁴ Rangé par Delnero s.v. iri₁₁-gal.

¹⁴⁵ Dans SANER 26, 344:100 K₁, on peut hésiter entre (...) na-na a/e₄-ya na-na et na-na-a ya na-na; le petit espace entre a/e₄ et ya plaide pour la seconde solution (de même Delnero 232, etc.). Remarquer que la lecture ya doit reposer sur une collation; le signe copié est différent.

¹⁴⁶ zi-ge = zi-gen₇.

¹⁴⁷ V. la note précédente.

zu-bi = suba₍₂₎: 241 sq. l. 20'.
 zu-bi₂ = suba₍₂₎: 538, 600, 645.
 zu-bi₂ la = suba₍₂₎ la₂: 241 sq. l. 20'.
 zu-en = ^dsuen: 538, 543, 600, 619, 645.
 zu-lu-m = su₁₁-lum: 565¹⁴⁸, 645.

3) Liste des lexèmes

a: → a₂.
 a: V. e₄/a.
 a-a: → (*)a-ya, ya.
 a-ab-ba: → a-a-ba.
 a-a-ugu: → a-ya-gu.
 a-eštub: e-a-tu-ub, e₂-a-tu-ub, e₂-a-aš-tu-ub.
 a-gar₃: → a-ga-ar.
 a-gar₃-a-gar₃: → a-ga-ar-a-ga-ar.
 a-gin₇: → a-nin, e-ge-en, e-gi, e₂-gi.
 a-la-lu: → al-lu.
 a-la₂: → a-la.
 a-na: → e-ya-na-aĝ₂, na.
^da-nun-na: → a-nu-na.
 a-pap: → a-pa-ap.
 a-ra-li: → (n)a-ra-[li].
 a-ri-a: → a-ra-a.
 a-ša₃(-g): → a-ša, a-ša-g, ša₃.
 a-še-er: → a-ši-r, a-ši-ir, (m)a-še-[...] .
 a₂: → a, a(n), (n)a; v. aussi ^den-a₂-nun.
 a₂-nu-ĝal₂: → a-nu-ĝa₂.
 a₂-nun-ĝal₂: → a₂-nu-ĝa₂.
 a₂-sig₃: → a-sa-g.
 a₂-ur₂: → a-u₂-r, a-u₃-r, a-u₃-ur, a-u₄-r, a-ur, a-ur₂.
 ab: → a-b.
 ab-lal₃: → ab-la-al.
 ab-sin₂: → ab-si(-n), ab-si-im, *ab-si-in.
 ab₂: → ab.
 abgal: → ab-ka-l...
 abzū: → ab-za, (*)ab-zu.
 ad: → a-d.
 ad-da: → a-da.
 ad₆: → a-t, *ad, at-t.
 adab^{ki}: → a-ra-b.
 adab(u)^{ki}: → a-du-bu.
 addir: → ad-te-r.
 aĝ₂: → a, an, ĝ(u₁₀); v. aussi ki-aĝ₂.
 aĝ₂-bara₃-ga: → aĝ₂-ba-ra-ga, am-ba-ra-ga.
 aĝ₂-ma-al: → aĝ₂-ma-l.
 aĝarin₄: → a-ĝa₂-ri-in
 AK: → a, a-q, (ĝ)a₂-k, ke, (n)a, (n)a-k, ša; v. aussi kar-kid₂, niĝ₂-AK-a, ur-šu-AK-a.
^{ĝes}al-ĝar-sur-ra: → al-ĝa₂-ar-sur-ra.
 alan: → a-la-n.
 alim: → a-li, a-li-m, *a-li-im.
 am: → a, "a-m", am₃.
 ama: → (*)a-ma, am; (d)a-am, ma, ma₂.
 ama-gan: → e-mi-ga.
 ama-ugu: → ama-gu₂.
 ama-ušumgal-an-na: → a-ma-u₂-šu-ga-la-na, am-išib-gal-an-na, ama-šu-ga-la-na, ama-šu-gal-a-na, ama-šu-gal-la-na, ama-šu-mu-gal-la-na, ama-u₃-šu-gal-la-na, ama-u₃-šu-um-gal-an-na.
 amalu: → a-ma-lu, ama-lu, ama-lu₂.
 amaš: → a-ma-s, (*)a-ma-aš₂, ama-s, ama-maš, (g)i-maš, ma-s, mas₂-s, u₃-maš; comp. e₂-maš.
 ambar: → *a-ba-ar, *a-bar, a-pa-ar, *ab-ba-ar, *ab-bar, ap-pa-r, ap-pa-ar.

¹⁴⁸ Lire zu-lu-um, pas su-lu-um.

an: → a, a-n, aĝ₂, al, (ĝi)n, (k)a, (l)a-n, (m)a-n, (n)a, (n)a-n, (n)a-an, (r)a, (r)a-n, (y)a-n; v. aussi ama-ušumgal-an-na, dubur-an-na, dur-an-ki, e₂-an-na, ga-ša-an-an-na, mu-tin-an-na, ušumgal-an-na.
 an-dul₃: an-de-el, an-di-il₃.
 an-edin: → an-di-n.
 an-pa: → an-pa₃.
 anše: → a-ši, an-ši; v. aussi maš₂-anše.
 ar₂: → a-r.
 aratta^{ki}: → a-ra-ta, a-ra-^rta₃[?].
 arḥuš: → ar-ḥu-š, *ar-ḥu-uš.
^dasal-lu₂-ḥi: → a-sa-al-lu-ḥi.
^{ĝi}asal₂: → a-sa-l, a-sa-al.
^dasar: → a-sa-r.
 aš: → a-š, aS₃-s.
 aš-te: → aš-ti, eš-de.
 aš₂-bala: → a-aš₂-pa-la.
^{munus}aš₂-gar₃: → iš-gar₃.
 babbar: → *ba-ab-ba-ar, ba-ap-pa-ar, ba-ba-r, (*)ba-ba-ar, ba-pa-r, pa-pa-ar; v. aussi ^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂.
 babbar/bar₆: → bar.
 bad: → (*)ba-ad, *ba-da, pa-t.
 bad₃: → ba-d, ba-ad, bad, *pa-a.
 bala: → ba-la, (i)b-la, pa-la; v. aussi aš₂-bala, ki-bala.
 bala-e: → (i)b-l(e).
 balaĝ: → ba-la-ĝ, ba-la-aĝ₂.
 ban₃-da: → ba-an-da, ban₃-ta.
 bad₃-tibira^{ki}: → ba-di-bi-ra, bad-bi-ra.
^{ĝi}bansur: → ba-an-su-r, ba-an-su-ur, *ba-an-šur, pa-an-su-ur₂, *pa-an-šu^r-ur^r, pa₃-an-su-r.
 bar (subst. et vb.): → ba-r, (*)ba-ar, bar^{ar}; v. aussi eš-bar, ur-bar-ra, uru₂-bar.
 bar-bar: → ba-ba-ar.
 bar-dul₅: → bar-du-ul.
 bara₂(-g): → "ba-ra", pa-ra(-g).
 bara₃(-g): → ba-ra, ba-ra-g; v. aussi aĝ₂-bara₃-ga.
 bil₍₂₎-la₂-bi: → bi-la-bi.
 bil₂-la₂: → bi-la.
 bir₅: → bi-ir.
 bir₇-bir₇: → bi-ir-bi-r.
 biri: → bi-ri.
 bulug: → bu-lu-k, (*)bu-lu-ug, *mu-lu-ug.
 bur₂-bur₂: → bu-ur-bu-r.
ⁱ⁷buranun: → bu-ra-na.
 buru₃^{mušen}: → (*)bu-ru.
 buru₁₄: → (i)b-ru s.v. ki-buru₁₄.
 dab₅: → da-b, da-p, *da-ab, ta-b.
 dadag: → da-da-g, *da-da-ag.
 daĝal: → da-ĝa₂-l, (*)da-ĝal₂, da-ka-l, da-ma-l, da-ma-al.
 daḥ: → ta-ḥ.
 dal: → da-l, (*)da-al.
 dal-dal-dal: → da-al-da-dal.
 dal-la: → dalla, ta-al-[-...].
 dam: → da, da-m, (*)da-am, da-ma, dam-ma.
 dam-gar₃: → dam-ga-ar, dam-ga-ra.
 dar-dar: → da-ar-da-r.
 de₂: → de.
 de₂-de₂: → de₃-de₃..
 de₅-g: V. na-de₅-g.
 de₆: → de.
 di: → *de-e, *di-i, ti; v. aussi maḥ-di.
 di-di: → de₃-de₃.
 di-ku₅: → di-ku.
 di₄-di₄-la₂: → de-de-el, de-de-le, de-de₃-el-le, de₃-de₃-la, de₃-el-le.
 dib: → da-p, di-b, di-p, *di-ib.
 dib-dib: → di-di-b.
 diĝir: → di-gi-r, *di-ĝi₆-ir, di-ne-er, DIĜIR^{ĝe9/ne-r}, DIĜIR^{ĝe9/me-cr}.

^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂: → de-el-en-babbar₂, di-li-babbar₂, di-li-bar.
dili: → *de-e-li, (*di-li, *du-li, (u)d-li.
dili₂: V. šen-dili₂.
dim: → di-m.
dim₂: → di-m, di-im; v. aussi niĝ₂-dim₂-ma, niĝ₂-ḥul-dim₂-ma.
dim₂-dim₂: → di-di(-m).
dim₃: → di-m.
dim₃-me-er: → di-me-er, di-mi-ir, dim₃-me-r, dim₃-mi-ir.
^šdimgul: → di-im-gu-ul.
diri: → (*di-ri.
du₃: → du, *du-u₂, (i)t-tu, tu.
du₃-du₃: → du-du.
du₅-mu: → "du-mu".
dumu: → (*du-mu.
du₆: → du.
du₇: → du, *du-u₂, du₃, du₁₀.
du₈: → du; v. aussi igi du₈.
du₈-du₈: → du-tu.
du₁₀(-g): → du, du-g, du₈; v. aussi niĝ₂-du₁₀-g.
du₁₁(-g): → du, du-g, du-k, du-q, du₇, du₈, tu-g.
du₁₂: → du.
du₁₂-du₁₂: → du-du; v. aussi duudu_x/du₁₂-du₁₂.
du₁₄: → du.
dub: → *du-ub, dub₂, tu-b.
dub-sar: → du-ub²-sa-ar, du₁₀-sa-r, dub-sa-r.
dub₂: → dub, tu-b, tu-p, (*tu-ub.
dub₂-dub₂: → tu-tu-b, tu-tu-ub.
dubur: → du-bu-r.
dubur-an-na: → du-bu-ra-na, du-^rx^r-ar-ra-na.
duudu_x/du₁₂-du₁₂: *du-ud-du.
dug: → du, du(-k).
dugud: → (*du-gu-ud..
dul: → du-l, *du-ul.
dul₅: → du-ul; v. aussi bar-dul₅.
dumu: → mu, tu-mu.
dungu: → du₁₀-gu.
dur-an-ki: → du-ra-an-ki.
dur₂: → du-r, du-ru/du-r, *du-ur.
dur₁₁-ra: → du-ra.
duru⁽ⁿ⁾: → du-ru, dur₁₁-ra.
durun: → du-ru.
durun/dur₂-ru-un: → du-ru-n.
durun-durun: → du-ru-du-ru-n.
dusi₂: → du-si.
e: → (b)i₂, (n)i, (p)e; v. aussi mi = {m + e}.
e-g/eg₂: → e₂-g, eg, ge.
e-lum: → a-lu-m, el-lu-um, lum.
e-ne: → i-ni.
e-ne-eĝ₃: → i-ne-eĝ₃, i-ni, i-ni-ĝ, i-ni-k, i-ni-m, i-ni-im, ne-eĝ₃, ni-ĝ.
(e-)re₇: → e-re, e-ri-i(š), re, *re-e, (š)i-re.
e-sir₂: → e-si-r, e-si-ir.
e₂: → (*e, e₂-y, (ĝ)e₆, ya.
e₂-an-na: → a-a-an-na, e₂-a-na, e₂-ya-na.
e₂-eš₂-dam: → (d)a-aš-ta-am.
e₂-gal: → e-gal; v. aussi ^dnin-e₂-gal-la.
e₂-kiš-nu-ĝal₂: e-ki-iš-nu-ĝal₂.
e₂-kur: → (b)e₂-kur.
e₂-maš: → i-ma-š; comp. amaš.
e₂-SAR-ra: → e₂-sa-ra.
e₃: → (*e, e₂, (m)e, (n)e₂; v. aussi pa-e₃.
e₃-d: → (b)e₂-d.
e₃-a: → a.

e₄/a: → (*e, e₂, e(n)).
 edin: → di-n, e-di-n, e₂-di-n; v. aussi an-edin.
 eg₂: V. e-g/eg₂.
 egi₂: → (*e-gi.
 egir: → *e-gi-ir, gi-r(e).
 ê^{is}ellaĝ: → *el-la-aĝ₂.
 eme: → e-me, i-me.
 emeda: → e-mi-da.
 en: → e-n, e₂-n, i-n, in.
^den-a₂-nun: → e₂-na-na, en-a-nu-un.
^den-ki(-k): → ^de-ki-ki, in-ki-k, (n)i-in-ki, (n)i-in-ki-id.
^den-lil₂: → (^d)e-li-l, e₂-le-el.
 en₂-e₂-nu-ru: → en-ni-in-nu-ra; v. aussi tu₆ en₂-e₂-nu-ru.
 en₃: → e-ne, en.
 en₃-ša₄: → en-ša₄.
 en₃-še₃: → en-še.
 en₃-tar: → en-tar.
 engar: → e-ga-r.
 engur: → *en-gu-ur, *en-gur.
 ensi: → im-si.
 ensi₂: → "e-si", in-si.
 er₂-šem₅-ma: → er₂-si-ma.
 ereš₃: → e-re-eš.
 eridu^{ki}: → a/e₄-ri-du^{ki}, e-ri-du.
 erim₂: → (*e-ri-im, i-ri-m, i-ri-im.
 erim₂-ĝal₂: → i-ri-ĝal₂-al.
 erim₃: → e-ri-im, *i-ri-im-ma, i-ri-ma.
 ê^{cs}erin: → *e-re-en, e-ri-im, e-ri-in, ri-n.
 eš-bar: → eš-ba-r.
 eš₂-dam: → aš-ta-am.
 eš₃: → uš.
 eš₃-dam: → eš-dam.
 eštub: → a-tu-ub, aš-tu-ub; v. aussi a-eštub.
^dezinam: → e-zi-na-am.
^dezinam-^dku₃-su₃: → e-zi-na-ku-ru-si-ga.
 ga (vb.): → qa.
 ga-am₃ (ES de ga₆-ĝ): → qa.
 ga-ša-an: → ga-ša, ga-ša-n/n(a), ka-ša, ka-ša-n, ka-ša-an
 ga-ša-an-an-na: → ga-ša-an-an, ga-ša-an-na, ga-ša-an-na-an-na, ga-ša-an-na-na, ga-ša-na, ga-ša-na-an, ga-ša-na-na, ka-ša-aĝ₂-na-na, ka-ša-an-na, ka-ša-an-na-na, ka-ša-na-na, NIN-an-na, NIN-na-na.
 ga-ša-an-tin-ug₅-ba: → ga-ša-an-di-lu-ba, ga-ša-an-ti-il-lu-ba.
 gab₃: → *ga-ab, *ka-ab.
 gab₃(-bu): → ga-bu.
 gaba: → (*e)ga-ba.
 gakkul: → gu-ku-l.
 gal: → ga, ga-l, ga-al, "ga-al-la"; v. aussi e₂-gal, ^dir₃-ra-gal, iri₁₁-gal, lugal, nun-gal, sur₉-gal, /urugal/, ušumgal.
 gal-gal: → ga-al-ga, ga-al-ga-l, gal-ga-al.
 GAM.GAM, gīgurum: → gi-gi-ru-m.
 gam-gam^{mušen}: → ka-am-ka-am.
 gan: V. ama-gan.
 gana₂: → ga-na, qa-na.
 gana₂-gana₂: ga-na-qa-na.
 gaz: → ga-az.
 gaz-gaz: → ga-ka-az.
 geg₂/gegge-g, "ĝi₆": → "gi = ĝi₆", ki-gi-k.
 geg₂-ga: gi-gi.
 gegge-ga: → gi-ki-ga; v. aussi saĝ-gegge-ga.
 gi (jeune femme): → ki, qa.
 gi (roseau): → ki; v. aussi ĝiš-gi.
 gi-gun₄-na: → gi-gu₂-na, gi₄-ku-na.
 gi-in: → gi-iĝ₃.
 gi-izi-la₂: → gi-zi-la.

gi-le-eĝ₃: → gi-le(-ĝ).
 gi-rin: → gi-ri-in.
 gi₄: → gi, gi-y, ki; v. aussi šu-mar-gi₄.
 gi₄-gi₄: → gi-gi, gi-ir-gi-r(e), gig, gig-gig, ki-gi, ki-gig.
 gi₄-in: → gi.
 gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: → gi-le(-ĝ), gi-le-^reĝ₃[?], gi-le-em; v. aussi na-aĝ₂-gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃.
 gi₁₆-gi₁₆-le: → gi-gi-lu.
 gi₁₆-sa: → gi-sa.
 gid₂: → gi-d.
 gitim: → *ki-te, *ki-ti, (*)ki-ti-im, *ki-tim.
 gig: → gi, ki-g; v. aussi ki-gig, mu-gi₁₇-ib/mu-gig, nu-gig.
 gig(-ga): → gi-g(a), gi₄-g(a), ki-g(a).
 gig-gig: → gi₄-gi₄.
^{ĝi₈}giĝir: → gi-gi-r, *gi-gi-ir, gi-qa-r, gi-qa-ir.
 giĝurum: V. GAM.GAM.
 gi₄-lu^{mu₃en}: → gi-ri-lu^{ĝe-en}.
 gu₂: → gu, gu₄; v. aussi nam-gu₂.
 gu₃: → gu, gu₂.
 gu₄: → gu, u₂-u(d).
 gub: → gi-b, gu-b, (*)gu-ub, gup-p.
 gub-gub: → gu-gu-ub, gu-ub-gub.
 gul(-gul): → gu-l, gu-ul-gu-ul, (*)gu-ul, gu₄-ul-gu₄-ul, gul-UL, ku-l, ku-ul(-ku-ul).
 gum-gum: gu-um-gu-um.
 gun₃: → (*)gu-nu, ku-nu.
 gun₃-gun₃: gu-un-gu-nu.
 gur: → gu, gu-r, *gu-ur.
 gur-gur: gu-ur-gu-r, ku-ur₂-ku-r.
 gur₃: → gur, (i)g-ru.
 gur₃-ru: → gur-u₃.
 gurum: → gi-ru, ku-ru-m.
 ĝa₂-nun-maĥ: → ĝa₂-nu-ma-aĥ.
 ĝal₂: → ĝa₂, ĝa₂-l, ĝa₂-al; v. aussi erim₂-ĝal₂, ĥe₂-ĝal₂, ĥul-ĝal₂, ku₃-ĝal₂, niĝ₂-zi-ĝal₂.
 ĝar: → amar, ĝa₂-r, ĝa₂-ar; v. aussi niĝ₂(-)-ĝar-ra.
 ĝeštīn: → ne-ti, ne-ti-in.
 ĝeštug₂: → *ĝe₆-eš-tu, ni-iš-tu.
 "ĝi₆ 'noir'": V. geg₂.
 ĝi₆-par₃: → ĝi₆-ba-r, ĝi₆-pa-r, ni₅-pa-ar.
 ĝi₆-u₃-na: → ĝi₆-ĝu₁₀-na.
 ĝin/ĝen: → ĝa₂-n, *ĝe₆-en, ĝi₆, ĝi₆-n/mi-n, ĝi₆-in.
 ĝir₂: → ĝir₃.
 ĝiri₃: → ĝiri₂.
 ĝi₈: → ĝi₆-iš.
 ĝi₈-gi: → ne₂-eš-ki, ni-iš-gi, ni₅-iš-gi.
 ĝi₈-ĥur: → ĝi₈-ĥu-ur₂, ni-iš-ĥu-ur.
 ĝi₈-nu₂: → ĝi₈-nu.
 ĝi₈-ur₃: → mu-su-ur.
 ĝi₈₃: → ĝi₈, ni-iš.
 ĝuruš: → ku-ru-uš.
 ĥa-lam: → ĥa-la-m.
^{ĝi₈}ĥa-lu-ub₂: → ĥu-lu-ub.
 ĥa-mun: → ĥa-mu-n.
 ĥa-šu-ur₂: → ĥa-šu-r.
 ĥal-ĥal: → ĥa-ĥa-al.
¹ĥal-ĥal: → ĥa-al-ĥa-al.
 ĥar-ra-an: → ĥa-ra-n, ĥar-ra-n.
^{ĝi₈}ĥašĥur: → *ĥa-aš-ĥu-ur, ĥa-aš-ĥu-ur₂, ĥa-aš-ku-r, ĥa-aš₂-ĥu-r, *ĥa-aš₂-ĥu-ur, ĥa-šu-r.
 ĥe₂-du₇: → ĥe₂-du₁₀.
 ĥe₂-ĝal₂: → ĥe-ĝa₂-l, ĥe-ĝa₂-al, ĥe-ĝal₂.
^{ĝi₈}ĥenbur: → ^{mu}ĥi-bu-ur₂.
 ĥenbur₂: → ĥa-am-bu-r.
⁴ĥendur-saĝ-ĝa₂: → ĥa-an-du-ur-sa-ĝa₂, *ĥe-en-du-ur-saĝ.
 ĥeš₅: → ĥi-iš.

ħir: → ħi-ir.
 ħu-bu-ur₂: → ħu-bu-r, ħu-bur.
 ħu-luħ: → ħu-lu-ħ.
 ħuġ/ħun: ħu-ġ, *ħu-un.
 ħul: → ħu-l, (*ħu-lu, (*ħu-ul, ħul-lu, lu, (u)ħ-lu; v. aussi niġ₂-ħul-dim₂-ma, u₄ ħul.
 ħul-ġal₂: → ħu-lu-ġal₂-l, ħu-un-ġal₂, ħu-ur-ġal₂-l.
 ĤUL.ĤUL: → ħu-ħu, ħu-ul-ħu-ul, ħul-ħu-lu, ħul-lu-ħul-l.
 ħul-a: → (a)ħ-la, (u)ħ-la.
 ħul (devant /e/): → (u)ħ-le.
 ħul₂: → ħu-l, (*ħu-ul, ħul.
 ħul₂-la-ħul₂-la: → ħu-la-ħu-la.
 ħur: → ħu-ur, ħu-ur₂; v. aussi ġiś-ħur.
 ħur-saġ: → ħu-saġ, ħu-ur-su-g, ħu-ur₂-sa₂-ġ, ħur-sa-ġ, ur₂-saġ; v. aussi ^dnin-ħur-saġ.
 ħuš: → ħu-ś, ħu-uś.
 i: → e.
 i-r: → (b)i-r.
 i-bi₂: → i-bi.
 i-dub: → i-tu-ub.
 i-lu: → e-lu₂, el-lu, i₃-lu, (n)i-lu.
 i-si-iś: → i-si-ś(i), "i-si-iś".
 i₃: → (*i).
 i₃-si-in^{ki}: → i-si-n, i-si-in^{ki}, i₃-si-n.
 i₇(-d): → e, (*i), i-d, id, (ś)i-d.
 ib₂: → *ib.
ⁱ⁷idigna: → i-ig-la.
 igi: → (*i)-gi.
 igi dus: → igi du.
 igi-nim-ma: → igi-na-ma.
 il₂: → el, i-l, il, (n)i-l.
 il₂-il₂: → il-lil₂, il₂-lil₂.
^{ġiś}ildag: → el-de-eg.
 ildum₂: → il-tu-ub.
 im-ma-al: → i-ma-al.
 im₂: → en, im; v. aussi ^ddili(i)-im₂-babbar₂.
 imma₃: → im-ma; v. aussi ^dnin-imma₃.
^dinana: → NI-na-na.
^dindag(a)ra: → in-da-ag-ra.
 inim: → i-ni-m, i-ni-im, *i-nim; v. aussi ka-inim-ma.
 inim-ġar: → i-ni-ġar.
 ir-ir: → (m)i-ir.
 ir₂: → a-ar, i-r, i₃-r, ir, (n)i-r.
 ir₂-ša₃-ne-ša₄: → ir-ša-ni-ša.
 ir₂-še₃ še₂₂-še₂₂: → i-še še-še, ir-ši še-še.
 ir₂ še₂₂-še₂₂: → ir ši-ši.
^dir₃-ra-gal: → ir-ra-ga-al.
 ir₉: → ir₂.
 iri/eri: → e-ri, *i-ri.
 iri₁₁-gal: → i-ri-ga-al.
 isla: → e-zi-la.
^dištaran: → e-ze₂-ra.
 iti₆: → i-ti, i-ti-d.
 izi: → i-zi, zi; v. aussi gi-izi-la₂.
 ka-inim-ma: → ka-i-ni-ma.
 ka-na-aġ₂: → (i)g-na-ġ, ka-ġ, ka-ġa₂, ka-na, ka-na-ġ, ka-na-m, ka-na-am, ka-nam.
 ka-tar: → ka-ta-ar.
 ka-teś₂: → ga-te-eś.
 ka₂/KA₂: → *a-ka, *ka, ka-aġ₂-ka-an, *ka-an-ka-an.
 kal: → ka-al.
 kalag-ga: → ka-la-ak-ka.
 kalam: → ka-la-am, ka-na-m.
 kar: → ka-ar.
 kar-kid₂: → ka-ki-d.

kas₄: → ka-s, *ka-aš₂.
kaš: → ka, (*)ka-aš.
keš₂: → i-ik-še, (i)k-še, ki-ši.
keš₂-keš₂-d: → ki-ki-ši-d.
keš₃^{ki}: → ke-eš, keš.
ki-aĝ₂: → ki-ga-aĝ₂.
ki-bala: → ki-ba-la, ki-ib-la.
ki-buru₁₄: → ki-ib-ru.
ki-en-gi(-r): → ki-i₃-ki, ki-in-gi-r.
ki-gig: → ki-gi.
ki-si₃-ga: → ki-si-qa.
ki-sikil: → ki-is₃-ki-r, ki-iš-ke-el, ki-iš-ki-il, ki-iš-ki-il₂, ki-si-ki.
ki-tuš: → ki-tu-š, ki-tu-uš, ku-tu-uš.
ki-ur₃: → ki-u₃-r, ki-ur.
kid₂: → ki-d.
kilim: → gi-li, gi-li-li.
kin-gi₄: → ki-en-gi₄.
kiri₃: → gi-ir, (*)gi-ri, *ki-ri.
kiri₃-zal: → gi-ir-za-al, gir-zal.
kiri₆: → ki-ir, ki-ri.
kisal: → ki-sa-l, *ki-sa-al, ki-sa₂-al.
kiš^{ki}: → ki-š.
kiš₈: → ki-še.
ku-li: → gu-li.
ku₂: → (*)gu, *gu-u₂, (*)gu₂, *gu₂-u₂, ku.
ku₃(-g): ku, ku-g, ku-k, *ku-u₂, ku-uk.
ku₃-ĝal₂: → ku-ĝa₂-l.
^dku₃-su₃: → ku-su, ku-us₂-su; v. aussi ^dezinam-^dku₃-su₃.
ku₃-zu: → ku-zu.
ku₄-ku₄: → ku-ku, kur-kur.
ku₅(-d/r): → (*)ku, ku-d, ku-r, ku-t, *ku-u₂.
kul-aba^{ki}: → ku-la-ab, ku-la-ba, ku-ul-la-ba.
kun: → ku-un.
kur: → ku-r, ku-ur, ku-ur₂.
kur-ĝar-ra: → ku₃-ĝa₂-ra, kur-ĝa₂-ra.
kur-kur: → ku-u₄-gu-r, kur-ku-r.
kur₂: → gu-ur, ku-r, kur.
kur₄: → *kur.
kurku₂: → ku-kur, ku-ur-ku, ku-ur₂-ku, kur-ku, kur-kur.
kuš₂: → ku-š.
la-ra-ak^{ki}, la₇-ra₃-ak^{ki} → la-ra-g.
la₂: → (i)l-la, la; v. aussi gi-izi-la₂, sum₄-la₂, sum₄-la₂-sum₄-la₂, unu₂ la₂.
la₂-e/la₂ devant /e/: → le, (u)l-le.
la₇-ra₃-ak^{ki} → la-ra-g.
lagaš^{ki}: → la-ga-s.
laḥ₄: → la-ḥ, *la-aḥ.
lal₃: → la-al.
lam-lam: → la₂-la₂.
li-bi-ir: → li-bi-ir.
lib: → li-l.
lil₂: → li-l, *li-il.
lil₂-la₂: → al-la.
lil₂-la₂(-en-na): → e₂-lil₂(-na).
limmu₂: → li-mu; v. aussi niĝ₂-ur₂-limmu₂.
lu: → la.
lu-lim, lulim: → lu-li-im, lu-li-im, *lu-li-im, *lu-lim.
lu₂: → lu.
lu₂-ulu₃: → lu-lu, lu₂-lu, lu₂-lu₂, lu₂-lu₂(-u₄); v. aussi na-aĝ₂-lu₂-ulu₃, nam-lu₂-ulu₃.
lu₃-lu₃: → lu-lu, lul-la.
lugal: → lu-ga-l, lu₂-ga-l, lu₂-gal; v. aussi nam-lugal.
lulim: V. lu-lim.
lum-lum: → lu-lu-um.

ma-a-a: → ma-ya.
 ma-al: → ma, ma-l; v. aussi aĝ₂-ma-al.
 ma-nun: → ma-nu-n.
^{ĕs}ma₂: → ma.
 ma₂-du₃: → ma-tu.
^{is}ma₂-gurs: → ma-gu-ur₅.
 maĥ: → ma-ĥ, (*ma-aĥ; v. aussi ĝa₂-nun-maĥ.
 maĥ-di: → maĥ-ti.
 mar: → ma-r, ma-ar; v. aussi ŝu-mar-gi₄.
^dmar-tu: → ĝa₂-ar-^rdu^l.
 maš₍₂₎: V. amaš, e₂-maš.
 maš₂-anše: → maš-a-ši.
 maškim: → maš-gi-in.
 me: → (*me-e, mi.
 me "être": V. nu-me-a.
 me-a (participe de me): → ya.
 me-e: → (*me, mi, mi-i.
 me-en: → mi-en.
 me-er-si: → mi-ir-si.
 me-lam₂: → me-li-im, mi-li, mi-li-im, "ne-la₂-am".
 me-li-e-a: → me-li-ya.
 me-na(-še₃): → mi-na(-ši).
 me-ri "pied": → ĝa₂-ri, mi-ri.
 me-teš₂: → me-ti-eš, mi-te-iš(-e).
 me₃: → mi.
 men: → (*me-en.
 mi₂: → mi, mi-im.
 mi = {m + e}: → (m)i, mi-e.
 (tumu)mir: → ^{tu-mu}me-er, (*mi-ir, ^{tu-mi}mi-ri.
 mir-mir: → mi-ir-mi-ir.
 mu (nom): me.
 mu-gi₁₇-ib/mu-gig: → lu₂-gi-b, mu-gi, mu-gi-b, mu-gi-ib₂, mu-gi₄-ib, nu-gi.
 mu-lu: → (u)m-lu.
 mu-nim-mar: → mu-ni₅-in-ma-ar.
 mu-nu₂: mu-nu.
 mu-sar-ra: → mu-sa-ra.
 mu-tin: → mu-di-n, mu-ti-n, mu-ti-in, mu₂-ti-in.
 mu-tin-an-na: → mu-ti-na, mu-ti-na-na, mu₂-ti-na-na.
 mu-ud-na: → mu-ud-nu.
^dmu-ul-lil₂: → mu-le-el, mu-li, mu-li-l, (^d)mu-lil₂, mu-lu-l(u), mu-ul-la, ^dmu-ul-li, ^dmu-ul-li-l.
 mu-un-gar₃: → mu-ga-r.
 mu-un-gur₁₁: → ma-gI-ur.
 mu₂: → ma, mu, *mu-u₂.
 mu₁₁-mu₁₁: → mu-mu.
 mud: → mu-d, (*mu-ud; v. aussi ^dnu-dim₂-mud.
 mug: mu-g.
 mul: → (*mu-ul.
 mul-mul: → mu-ul-mu-ul.
 munus: *mu-nu-us₂, munus-s.
 mur-ša₄/ur₅-ša₄: → (*mu-ru-um-ša, mu-ru-um-šu-a, mu-ur-ša₄.
 murgu₂: → mu-ur-gu, *mur-gu₄.
 /muruš/ (ES pour ĝuruš): → mu-ru(-š).
 muš: → mu-uš, (u)m-mu-š.
 muš₃: → ma-aš, mu-š, mu-uš.
 mušen: → *mu-še-eĝ₃, *mu-še-en, mu-še₃, mu-ši-in.
 na-aĝ₂: → na, ^rna^l-ĝ, na-am.
 na-aĝ₂-gi₁₆-le-eĝ₃: → na-gi, na-gi-le-em.
 na-aĝ₂-lu₂-ulu₃: → na-aĝ₂-lu-lu.
 na-aĝ₂-tar: V. nam/na-aĝ₂-tar.
 na-de₅-g: → na-di-g.
 na-nam: → na-na, na-na-a.
 na₄: → i-ya.

naĝ: → (*na-ĝ(a), (*na-aĝ, *na-aĝ₂-ĝa₂, *na-ĝa₂.
 naĝar: → na-ĝa₂-r.
 nam: → na-m, na-am.
 nam-gu₂: → na-gu₄-u₈.
 nam-ĥe₂: → na-am-ĥa.
 nam-ĥe₂-a: → nam-ĥi-i-a.
 nam-lu₂-ulu₃: → nam-lu₂-lu₂.
 nam-lugal: → na-lu-ga-l.
 nam-nir: → na-am-ni-r.
 nam(2)-nun: → na-am-nu-un, nam-nu-n.
 nam-tag: → nam-da-g.
 nam/na-aĝ₂-tar: → na-am-ta-r, na-ta-r, nam-ta-r, nam-ta-ar.
 nam₂: → nam.
 nam-nir: V. ^dnu-nam-nir.
 nam₂-nun: V. nam(2)-nun.
^dnamma: → ^dna-na, ^dna-na-ma; v. aussi ur-^dnamma.
^dnanna: → na-na-ya.
 ne-saĝ: → me-saĝ.
 ni₂: → ne, ni, nis.
 ni₁₀-ni₁₀: → ni-ni, ni₅-nis.
 nibru^{ki}: → ni-ib-ru.
 nidba: → ni₅-in-ba.
 niĝ₂: → (*ni, ni-ig, *ni-iĝ₃, niG₂-g.
 niĝ₂-AK-a: → niĝ₂-ĝa₂-ka.
 niĝ₂-ba: → ni₅-ba.
 niĝ₂-dim₂-ma: → ni-im-di-im-ma.
 niĝ₂-du₁₀-g: → ne-du-g, ni₅-in-du-g.
 niĝ₂(-)ĝar-ra: → ne(-)ĝa₂-ra.
 niĝ₂-ĥul-dim₂-ma: → ni-im-ĥu-lu-di-ma, niĝ₂-ĥu-lu-di-ma.
 niĝ₂-su-ub: → ni-su-ub.
 niĝ₂-ur₂-limmu₂: → ne-ĝu₁₀-li-mu.
 niĝ₂-zi-ĝal₂: → ni-zi-ĝa₂-al.
 niĝin: → *ni-ge-en, *ni-ĝe₆-eĝ₃, *ni-ĝe₆-en, "ni-ĝi₆-in".
 niĝin₃-ĝar/mar: → ni-ĝa₂-r, ni-ĝa₂-ar, ni-ĝar, ni-iĝ₃-ĝar, ni-ma-r, niĝ₂-a₂-r.
^{ĝi₈}nim-mar: → ni-mi-mar; v. aussi mu-nim-mar.
 nimgir: → ni-mi-ir.
 nin: → *ne-en, *ni-in, nis.
^dnin-e₂-gal-la: → nin-e-gal-la.
^dnin-ĥur-saĝ: → niĝ₂-ĥu-ur-su-ga.
^dnin-imma₃: → ni-in-ni-im-ma.
^dnin-kilim: → ni-in-gi-li, niĝ₂-gi-li, niĝ₂-gi-li-li.
 nin₉: → ne-en, ni-n, (*ni-in.
 ninda: → in-da.
 nir: → ne-er, ni-r; v. aussi ^dnu-nam-nir.
 nisi: → ni-in-si.
 nita: → ni-in-ta.
 nitadam: → ni₅-ta-na.
^dnu-dim₂-mud: → ^dnu-dim₂-mu-d.
 nu-gig: → nu-gi₆-i-g, nu-ĝi(n).
 nu-me-a: → nu-ya.
^dnu-nam-nir: → nu-na-am-ni-r.
 nu-siki: → nu-uš-ki.
 nu₂: → nu, nu-um; v. aussi ĝi₈-nu₂, mu-nu₂.
 numun: → nu-mu.
^{u₂}numun₂: → nu-mu₂-un.
 nun: → na, nu, nu-n, (*nu-un; v. aussi ^da-nun-na, ^den-a₂-nun, ĝa₂-nun-maĥ, ma-nun, nam(2)-nun.
 nun-gal: → nu-ga-al.
 pa: → pa₃; v. aussi an-pa.
^dpa-bil₂-saĝ: → pa-bi-il-sa-aĝ₂.
 pa-e₃: → pa₃-e, pa₃-e₃; v. aussi ^dšul-pa-e₃.
 pa₅(-r): → pa, pa-r.
 pa(d)₃: → ba-d, pa-d, pa₃-d/r.

pap: → pa-ap.
 par₄: → *pa-ar.
 peš-peš (vb.): → pe-pe, pe-pe-eš.
 peš₂: → bi-iš.
 peš₁₀: → bi-š, bi-iš, pe-eš.
 piriġ: → pi-ri-iġ₃.
 pu₂: → (*pu, *pu-u₂.
 re₇: V. (e-)re₇.
 rib: → ri-b, *ri-ib.
 rig₇: → ri-g.
 sa-par₃: → sa-bar, sa₂-ab-ra.
 sa₂: → sa, su-a.
 sa₆(-g): → sa, sa-g.
 sa₆-sa₆: → sa₂-sa₂.
 sa₁₀: → sa.
 saġi: → sa-gi.
 saġ: → *sa, sa-g, sa-ġ, (*sa-aġ₂, sa-an, "sa₂", sa₂-ġ.
 saġ-gegge-ga: → sa-gi-ki-ga, saġ-ki-gi-ki-ak (= R-ka).
 saħar: → sa-ħa, sa-ħa-r, (*sa-ħa-ar.
 saħar₂: → (u)s₂-ħa-r.
 sanga₂: → ša-ġa₂.
 sar: → sa-r, sa-ar; v. aussi dub-sar, mu-sar-ra.
 sar-re: → (a)š₂-re.
 sar-sar: → sa-ar-sa-r, sa-sa-r.
 sed₅-sed₅: → si-si-d.
 si₃: → si.
 si₃-g: si-g, si-q; v. aussi ki-si₃-ga.
 si₃-si₃-g/k: → zi-zi-k.
 si₁₂-si₁₂: → "i-si-iš".
 sig₃: → sa₂-g, si-g.
 sig₃-sig₃: → sa₂-sa₂-g.
 siki: → si-ki, (u)š-ki; v. aussi nu-siki.
 sikil: → *si-ke-el, si-ki, (*si-ki-il; v. aussi ki-sikil.
 sila: → (a)š(-)si-la, (*si-la.
 sila₄: → (*si-la, sila₃.
 sila₃-ġar: → sila₄-amar.
 silig: → si-li-g, *si-li-ig.
 silim: → si-li, si-li-m, (*si-li-im.
 silim-eš₂-am₃: → si-li-ši-a.
 sipa: → sa-pa, si-pa, si-pa₃-d.
 sizkur₂: → *se₂-eš-kur, *si₂-iš-ku-ur, *si₂-iš-kur, [ši]-iš-ku-r.
 su-din^{mušen}: → su-te-en.
 su-lim-ma: → si-ma.
 su₃: → su, su-ud.
 su₃-ra₂-aġ₂: → su-da-aġ₂.
 su₃-su₃: → su-us₂-su.
 su₆: → su, *su₂-um; comp. sum₄(-...).
 su₈-ba: → su-ba.
 su₁₁-lum: → su-lu-um, zu-lu-m.
 suba(2): → su-bi, su-bi₂, su₈-bi, zu-bi, zu-bi₂.
 suba(2) la₂: → zu-bi₂ la.
^dsud₃: → su-ud.
^dsuen: → su-en, zu-en.
 suħuš: → (*su-ħu-uš.
 sukkal: → su-qa-al.
 sukud: → su-ku-d, su-ku-t.
 sum₄-la₂: → su-la; comp. su₆.
 sum₄-la₂-sum₄-la₂: → su-um-la-su-la.
 sumun₂: → su-mu-n; comp. sun₂.
^dsumuqan: → su-mu-un-ga-an.
 sun₂: → su₃-n; comp. sumun₂.
 sur: → su-r, su-ur₂.

sur-sur: → su-ur-su-ur.
 sur₉-gal: → sur-ru-ga.
 ša₃: → ša.
 ša₃-b: → ša-p, ša₃-p.
 ša₃-ne-ša₄: V. ir₂-R.
 ša₄: → ša, šu-a; v. aussi ir₂-ša₃-ne-ša₄, mur-ša₄/ur₅-ša₄.
 šakir₃: → *sa-ki-ir, si-ki-ir, *ša-ki-ir.
 šar₂: → ša-ar.
 šar₂-šar₂: → ša-ar-ša-r, ša-ša-r.
 še ("grain"): → ši.
 še-eb: → ši-b.
 še-en-ka₆: → ši-in-ka.
 še-er: → še₃.
 še₂₂-še₂₂: → še-še, ši-še, ši-ši; v. aussi ir₂-še₃ še₂₂-še₂₂, ir₂ še₂₂-še₂₂.
 šeg₉-bar: → ši-bar.
 šeg₃: → še-ġ, ši.
 šem₅: V. er₂-šem₅-ma.
 šen: → še-n.
 šen-šen: → še-še-en.
 šen-dili₂: → še-en-di-li
 šeš: → *se-es, *se-eš₃, si-s, šeš-š.
 šim: → ši-m, ši-im; v. aussi u₂-šim.
 šim-bi: → šim-bi₂.
 šir₃: → si-r, (*si-ir, si-r(a), še₃-er.
 šu ("main") → ši.
 šu-mar-gi₄: → šu-ma-ar-gi.
 šu-um-du-um: → šu-um-du.
 šu₂: → šu.
 šu₂-šu₂: šu-šu.
 šub: → šu, šu-b, šu-ub.
 šub-šub: → šu-šu-ub.
 šubur: → su-bu-r.
 šud₃: → (*š)u-du, šu-du₆, šu-ud-da.
 šul: → si-il.
^dšul-pa-e₃: → su-pa₃-e.
 šum₂: → šu, šu₂.
^{u2}/šumun/ (ES de ^{u2}numun₂): → šu-mu₂-un.
^{u2}šumunda: V. ^{u2}/šumun/.
 šurum: → šu-^rru[?]-m.
 šuš₂-šuš₂: → su-su.
 ta-e-am₃: → da-a-a.
 tab: → ta-p, ta-ab.
 tag-tag: → ta-ta.
 tak₄: → ta-ak.
 tar: → ta-r, ta-ar; v. aussi ka-tar, nam/na-aġ₂-tar.
 te: → *te-e, t_i, *ti-e.
^{u2}teme₂: → de-me.
 teš₂: → (*te-eš, (*ti-eš; v. aussi ka-teš₂, me-teš₂.
 t_i: → tu.
 t_ibir: → ti-bi-r.
 t_igi: → ti-gi.
 t_il₃: → di-l, te-l, ti-el, ti-il, til.
 t_in: → ti-il, ti-in; v. aussi mu-tin.
 t_in-ugs-ga: → di-lu-ba, ti-il-lu-ba; v. aussi ga-ša-an-tin-ugs-ba.
 t_ir: → te-e-r, (*te-er, ti-r.
 t_ir-tir: → te-te-er.
 tu-d: → du-d.
 tu₅: → tu.
 tu₆: → tu.
 tu₆ en₂-e₂-nu-ru: → tu-ni-nu-ra.
 tu₁₁-b: → tu-b.
 tug₂/tu₉: → du, (*tu, *tu-u₂, *tu-u₄.

tuku: → (*)tu-ku.
 tuku-tuku: → tu-ut-ku.
 tukul: → *tu-ku-ul.
 tukur₂: → (i)t-ku-r.
 tum₂: → tu-m, *tu-u₂, tu-um.
 *tumu-e: → tu-mi, tu-mu, tu-ni.
 tur: → tu-r, tu-ur.
 tur-tur: → tu-tu, tu-tu-r, tu-tu-ur, *tu-ur-tu-ur.
 tur₃: → tu-r, tu-ur, tu-ur₂, tur.
 tuš: → tu, tu-s, tu-š, (*)tu-uš; v. aussi ki-tuš.
 u: → *u₄.
 u₂: → (k)u, u₃, u₄.
 u₂-a-e-u₂-a: → ya-ĝu₁₀-ya-ĝu₁₀.
 u₂-šim: → u₂-ši-im, u₃-ši-im.
 u₃ ("sommeil"): → u₂.
 u₂-gu: → u-gu₃, u₃-gu₂.
 u₃-li-li-la: → u₂-li-li-la.
 u₃-mu-un: → mu-un, u₂-mu, u₃, u₃-mu-n, u₄-mu-n.
 u₃-tu: → u₃-du.
 u₄(-d): → u₂, u₂-d, u₃, u₃-d.
 u₄ ħul: → u₄-lu.
^du₄-saħar₂-ra: → us₂-ħa-ra.
 u₅: → u₂, u₃.
 u₈: → u₂, u(m).
 ub₇: → ub.
 ubur: → u₃-bu-ur₂, (*)u₃-bur.
 ud₅: → u₂, u₃.
 udug: → u₂-du, u₂-du-ug.
 ug₅: → u₂, u₃-g; v. aussi tin-ug₅-ga.
 uga^{mušen}: → u₂-ga, u₃-ga, u₄-ga.
 ugnim: → ug-nu-um.
 ugu: → gu₂, u₃-ga, u₃-gu; v. aussi a-a-ugu, ama-ugu.
 uĝ₃: → u₃.
 ulu₃: → lu-lu.
 umbin: → um-bi.
 ummeda: → e-me-da.
 unken: → um-ke-n, um-MI-n, *un-ke-en.
 unu₂: → u₂-nu, u₃-nu.
 unu₂ la₂: → u₃-nu la.
 unug^{ki}: → u₃-nu-k, u₃-nu-q, u₃-nu [...].
 ur: → u₂-ur, u₄, u₄-r.
 ur-bar-ra: → ur₂-ba-ra.
 ur-maħ: → ur₂-ma-ħ.
 ur-^dnamma: → ur-^dna-na(-ma).
 ur-saĝ: → ur₂-saĝ.
 ur-šu-AK-a: → u₄-šu-a-qa.
 ur₂: → (ĝ)u₁₀, u₂-r, u₃-r, u₃-ur, (*)ur; v. aussi a₂-ur₂, niĝ₂-ur₂-limmu₂.
 ur₃: → u₂-r, ur; v. aussi ki-ur₃.
 ur₄: → "u₂-ru".
 ur₅-ša₄: V. mur-ša₄.
 urim₂^{ki}: → u₂-ri-m, u₃-ri-m, u₄-ri-m.
 urin: → u₂-ri-in.
 uru₂: → ru, u₂-ru, u₃, u₃-ra, u₃-ru, *u₄-ru, uru₂^{ru}.
 uru₂-bar: → ru-ba-r.
 uru₂-ze₂-eb^{ki}: → uru₂-zi-ib₂^{ki}.
 /urugal/: → *u₂-ru-ga-al, *uru-gal.
 usan: → su-an.
 us₂: → (m)u-s.
 uš₂: → *uš.
 uš₁₁: → uš.
 ušbar: → ur₂-bar.
 ušumgal: → išib-gal, šu-ga-l, šu-gal, u₂-šu-ga-l, u₂-šu-um-gal, u₃-gal, u₃-šu-gal, u₃-šu-um-gal, ušum-gal.

ušumgal-an-na: → u₃-šu-gal-a-na; v. aussi ama-ušumgal-an-na.
 ušur: → *u₂-šu-ur, *u₂-šu-ur₂, u₃-šu-r, *u₃-šu-ur, u₃-šu-ur₂, *u₄-šu-ur.
^dutu: → (r)u-^dutu, u₃-[tu], u₄-tu.
 utug₂: → u₂-tu-ug.
 za-e: → za-a(Š), ze₂, zi.
 za-gin₃: → za-gi, za-gi-n, (*)za-gi-in.
 za₃(-g): → za, za-g.
 za₃-mi₂: → za-am-me-en.
 zabalam^{ki}: → za-ba-la.
 zabar: → za-ba-r.
 zal: → za-l, (*)za-al, *za-ar; v. aussi kiri₃-zal.
 zal-zal: → za-al-za-al.
 zalag: → za-la-k, (*)za-la-ag.
 ze₂-eb: → zi, zi-ib₂; v. aussi uru₂-ze₂-eb^{ki}.
 ze₂-eĝ₃: → ze₂.
 ze₂-er-ze₂-er: → zi-ir-zi-ir.
 zi-g: → zi-q.
 zil₂: → zi-l, zi-il.
 zu₂: → zu.